

Analysis of Web Accessible Networks, Organizations and Groups

Task	<u>Analysis of Web Accessible Networks, Organizations and Groups</u>	
Context	The EC project LIVEWHAT (WP 6). Coordinators of this activity were: Maria Kousis (Dept. of Sociology and Center for Research & Studies in Humanities, Social Sciences & Pedagogics, University of Crete) and Yannis Tzitzikas (FORTH-ICS) This task was funded by the University of Crete.	
Description	Identification and analysis of networks, organizations and groups engaged in “alternative forms of resilience” as seen in recent solidarity and other social innovation practices across the nine countries which are involved in the LiveWHAT project (e.g. barter networks, food banks, time banks, alternative coins, free medical services, soup kitchens, etc.)	
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1 The Purpose

LIVEWHAT¹ (LIVING WITH HARD TIMES) is an FP7 EU Project (initiated on December 2013) that studies policy responses and citizens' resilience in times of crisis. The project brings together universities and an international advisory board of leading scientists from nine European countries. One of the actions in the project (which is related to Work Package 6) includes the identification of a wide range of networks, organizations and groups engaged in "alternative forms of resilience" as seen in recent solidarity and other social innovation practices across the nine countries which are involved in the project (e.g. barter networks, food banks, time banks, alternative coins, free medical services, soup kitchens, etc.) Towards this direction the project should organize and sample the available online material in order to code and analyze it.

Dr. Maria Kousis, which is the scientific responsible for University of Crete (UOC) (which participates in the project's consortium), communicated FORTH discussing the above requirements. Both sides agreed that FORTH could undertake these activities starting from June 1, 2015 and ending on June 30, 2015, and delivering the results after the end of that period. Furthermore the scientific responsible of UOC had the role of being a communication hub between the FORTH team and the LIVEWHAT consortium.

To this end, FORTH, defined the process for analyzing these contents by exploiting publicly available software, or developing new applications whenever required. In this deliverable we report the process that was followed for analyzing the networks of the nine counties and report the results of this analysis.

2 The Process

The entry point for the analysis process is a publicly accessible network. In other terms it is a website containing links to other sites. The purpose is to analyze the contents of the network and export them in a form suitable for further analysis (by humans). Since there is not a common format for these networks, each one of them requires a different approach for analyzing it; in some cases the list of sites in a network are inside a table, in other cases there are drop down lists that reveal information for these sites, etc. This practically means that we should handle each network in a different way. In the next section we will describe the tools and methods that we have used for extracting the contents from the hubs/ sub hubs. As regards the format for storing the results of the extraction, we agreed that a set of comma-separated-values (CSV) or tabular data (XLS format) is sufficient.

Since for each country there are more than one hubs, we will end up with more than one lists. Furthermore these lists could contain many duplicate entries. Apart from this in many cases the data has to be curated in many ways (i.e. validation of URLs, e-mails, contact info, etc.). To this end after the analysis of all the networks of a county we merged the produced lists into a single one using a data merging/ cleaning tool (i.e. see below a description of such a tool – the OpenRefine tool).

¹ <http://www.livewhat.unige.ch/>

Finally for the entries that have been extracted and contain a URL, the contents of that websites will be partially downloaded and stored to enable the offline browsing the sites.

3 The Tools

This section describes the tools we used for analyzing the networks. Some of these tools are publicly available tools, while others have been designed and developed for this purpose.

3.1 WebScrapper

WebScrapper is a JAVA application, developed by FORTH, for analyzing the contents of a website. WebScrapper takes as input the URL of the network, analyzes the contents of the network, and exports two files containing information about the identified sites: (a) a file (in XLS format) containing all the information about the identified sites and (b) a file (in TXT format) containing the URLs of the identified sites. The first file is intended for humans and for each identified site, it contains:

- A title
- The URL of the site
- Contact information (address, postal code, city)
- E-mail address
- A description
- The date it was created/updated

Of course these information are not always available (e.g. in many networks the date field is absent), therefore for each network we exported whatever is available. The second file is produced in order to be used from another application for downloading the contents of the sites.

3.2 Selenium

Selenium² offers a suite of tools for automating various functionalities with web browsers. Selenium offers the methods for enabling the test-automation for web-based applications. The entire suite of tools results in a rich set of testing functions specifically geared to the needs of testing of web applications of all types. These operations are highly flexible, allowing many options for locating UI elements and comparing expected test results against actual application behavior. One of Selenium's key features is the support for executing one's tests on multiple browser platforms.

The Selenium suite has been particularly useful in the cases where information from a hub/sub hub was not organized properly and it required a lot of user interactions (i.e. various clicks on several links) to retrieve the actual content. Selenium allowed us to mimic the user behavior and retrieve the required information.

3.3 Custom JavaScript procedures

JavaScript is a programming language used to make web pages interactive. For the creation of an interactive web page, the developer mixes the actual content with JavaScript

² <http://www.seleniumhq.org/>

functions. In some cases it might be easier to extract the contents of a web site, by downloading the website and modifying the JavaScript code to show the contents in a particular form (i.e. as CSV values).

3.4 OpenRefine

OpenRefine³ is an open-source application for data cleanup and data transformation to several formats. These functionalities are performed over a set of rows of data which are separated into different columns. This schema resembles the relational database tables schema. The user can then define the set of operations that will be performed over the rows, including the transformation of the values of a cell based on its contents or the contents of another cell, the creation of a new value in a cell based on other values in other cells. The cleaned data set can then be exported in a variety of different formats including CSV, XML, RDF, JSON, etc.

3.5 Wget

GNU Wget⁴ (which is available both under Windows and Linux) is a free utility for non-interactive download of files from the web. Wget is pre-installed in most Linux distributions; however there are also available installations for Windows OS. There are several options for running Wget; the ones that proved useful for our purposes were the following:

- `-r` : -recursive download; download all the files that can be found in the website
- `-l 0` : maximum recursion depth; 0 declares infinite depth, which means that it will download everything in the website, without any restrictions in the depth.
- `-i listOfSites.txt` : download the sites, using the URLs that exist in the file listOfSites.txt

3.6 WKhtmlTOPdf

Wkhtmltopdf⁵ is an open source tool (released under LGPL v3) for rendering HTML into PDF using the QT Webkit rendering engine. The toolkit takes as input the URL of a website (an html document) and produces the corresponding output into a pdf file. There are several binaries for various operating systems (Windows, Linux, OS X) and there is also the source code available for others.

4 The Results

This section provides a summary of the results from the analysis of the networks. At first we provide a summary of the results for the networks of all the nine countries, as they have been derived after the data clean up / data merging activities. Afterwards we will provide the detailed results for each country.

4.1 Summary of the results

The following table shows the results from the analysis of the networks of the nine countries. The table contains the number of distinct entries that have been recognized, as

³ <http://openrefine.org/>

⁴ <https://www.gnu.org/software/wget/>

⁵ <http://wkhtmltopdf.org/>

well as the information that exist for them. More specifically for each column (i.e. Title, URL, Contact, Description, e-mail, Date) we report the number of entries that contain the corresponding information.

Country	Number of Entries	Title	URL	Contact Info	Description	e-mail	Date
Greece	3656	✓(3656)	✓(3038)	✓(3480)	✓(748)	✓(814)	
Sweden	2001	✓(1953)	✓(1752)	✓(1943)	✓(1908)	✓(1837)	✓(18)
Germany	2505	✓(2494)	✓(1936)	✓(1993)	✓(350)	✓(1285)	✓(474)
France	2285	✓(2285)	✓(1381)	✓(1691)	✓(1581)	✓(448)	✓(927)
Spain	2025	✓(1982)	✓(1279)	✓(1134)	✓(558)	✓(1096)	✓(534)
Poland	4669	✓(4669)	✓(2553)	✓(4655)	✓(59)	✓(3165)	✓(4576)
Switzerland	1368	✓(1364)	✓(904)	✓(1165)	✓(162)	✓(938)	
Italy	3411	✓(3409)	✓(1748)	✓(3098)	✓(1477)	✓(2789)	✓(2042)
UK	24630	✓(24630)	✓(15990)	✓(23777)	✓(13566)	✓(5679)	✓(506)

Table 1. A summary of the results for the nine countries

4.2 Detailed results

4.2.1 Greece

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs	4
Number of individual websites	0

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

- [1]. <http://www.enallaktikos.gr>
- [2]. <http://www.solidarity4all.gr>
- [3]. <http://omikronproject.gr>
- [4]. <http://www.boroume.gr>

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact	E-Mail	Category	Description
[1]	3,357	✓	✓	✓			
[2]	380	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
[3]	379	✓	✓			✓	
[4]	656	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓

Table 2. The results from the analysis of the networks for Greece

4.2.2 Sweden

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs	2
Number of individual websites	17

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

- [1]. www.volontarbyran.org/for-organisationer/

- [2]. <http://vuxnabarn.nu/forum/stodgrupper-f56/sjalvhelpsgrupper-och-samtalsgrupper-sverige-t4488.html>

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact	E-Mail	Description	Dates
[1]	2,082	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
[2]	88	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Indiv.	16	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓

Table 3. The results from the analysis of the networks for Sweden

4.2.3 Germany

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs	11
Number of individual websites	0

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

- [1]. <http://www.solidarische-oekonomie.de>
- [2]. <http://www.mondamo.de/linklist>
- [3]. <http://www.friedenskooperative.de/netzwerk/links-hr.htm> (human rights)
- [4]. <http://www.tauschringportal.de> (time banks)
- [5]. <http://www.umsonstladen.de> (alternative consumption)
- [6]. <http://www.syndikat.org/de/links/> (alternative housing)
- [7]. http://konsumpf.de/?page_id=39 (critical consumption)
- [8]. <http://www.tafel.de/die-tafeln/tafel-suche/adressenliste.html>
- [9]. <http://www.arbeitslosenverband.org/mitgliedsverbaende/index.html>
- [10]. <http://medibueros.m-bient.com/standorte.html>
- [11]. <http://www.evangelische-obdachlosenhilfe.de/index.php/mitglieder.html>

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact	E-Mail	Description	Date
[1]	578	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
[2]	158	✓	✓	✓ (city)		✓	
[3]	58	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[4]	368	✓	✓	✓			✓
[5]	92	✓	✓	✓			
[6]	27	✓	✓	✓			
[7]	188	✓	✓			✓	
[8]	947	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[9]	5	✓	✓	✓			
[10]	34	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[11]	75	✓	✓	✓	✓		

Table 4. The results from the analysis of the networks for Germany

4.2.4 France

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs	13
Number of individual websites	0

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

- [1]. <https://www.colibris-lemouvement.org/colibris>

- [2]. <http://colibris.ning.com/groups>
- [3]. <http://mouves.org/>
- [4]. <http://www.portail-solidarite.org/domaines/economie-sociale-et-solidaire>
- [5]. <http://www.lelabo-ess.org/>
- [6]. <https://www.francebarter.coop/>
- [7]. <http://www.unaf.fr/spip.php?rubrique30>
- [12]. <http://www.reseau-amap.org/>
- [13]. <http://www.acrimed.org/>
- [14]. <http://www.institut-economie-circulaire.fr/>
- [15]. <http://www.artisansdumonde.org/boutiques-commerce-equitable.html>
- [16]. <http://cnlii.org/>
- [17]. <http://heterotopies.overblog.com/cartographie>

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact	E-Mail	Description	Date
[1]	52	✓	✓	✓ (person)	✓		
[2]	468	✓	✓	✓ (city)		✓	
[3]	36	✓	✓			✓	
[4]	297	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
[5]	105	✓		✓ (area)		✓	
[6]	59	✓	✓			✓	
[7]	62	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
[8]	533	✓	✓	✓			✓
[9]	41	✓	✓			✓	
[10]	127	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
[11]	151	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[12]	11	✓	✓			✓	
[13]	318	✓	✓	✓ (area)		✓	

Table 5. The results from the analysis of the networks for France

4.2.5 Spain

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs	10
Number of individual websites	0

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following

- [1]. <http://15mpedia.org/wiki/>
- [2]. <http://www.economiasolidaria.org/entidades>
- [3]. <http://www.mecambio.net/>
- [4]. <http://bdtonline.org>
- [5]. <http://www.redautogestion.com/directorio-autogestion>
- [6]. www.todoporlapraxis.es/?cat=1
- [7]. http://ludus.org.es/es/projects?province_id=31
- [8]. <http://www.nodo50.org/puzlea/ocupacion.htm>
- [9]. <http://auditoriaciudadana.net/>
- [10]. <http://www.hispacoop.es/home>

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact	E-Mail	Description	Date
[1]	876	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[2]	406	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
[3]	67	✓	✓			✓	
[4]	307	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[5]	24	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
[6]	58	✓	✓			✓	✓
[7]	83	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
[8]	69	✓	✓		✓		
[9]	23	✓	✓		✓		
[10]	170	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓

Table 6. The results from the analysis of the networks for Spain

4.2.6 Poland

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs	8
Number of individual websites	27

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

- [1]. <http://www.ekonomiaspoleczna.pl/>
- [2]. http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&szukanie=zaawans1&kryt_typ_instyt_multi=74&baza=13
- [3]. http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&szukanie=zaawans1&kryt_typ_instyt_multi=83&baza=64
- [4]. http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&szukanie=zaawans1&kryt_typ_instyt_multi=114&baza=105
- [5]. http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&szukanie=zaawans1&kryt_typ_instyt_multi=89&baza=78
- [6]. <http://inkubatory.pl/mapa-inkubatorow/>
- [7]. <http://www.ffi.org.pl/pl/czlonkowie>
- [8]. <https://kolektywnie.wordpress.com/category/kooperatywy-spozywcze/>
- [9]. http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&kryt_nazwa=&kryt_miasto=&kryt_woj=&kryt_pola=12&kryt_typ_instyt_multi=17&baza=1&szukanie=zaawans1
- [10]. http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&kryt_nazwa=&kryt_miasto=&kryt_kraj=&kryt_ekk=8&szukanie=ekk
- [11]. http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&kryt_nazwa=&kryt_miasto=&kryt_woj=&kryt_pola=24&kryt_typ_instyt_multi=17&baza=1&szukanie=zaawans1

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact	E-Mail	Date	Description
[1]	39	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
[2]	147	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[3]	53	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[4]	97	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[5]	1149	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[6]	49	✓		✓			✓
[7]	12	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
[8]	27	✓	✓	✓ (city)			
[9]	1600	✓	✓	✓		✓	

[10]	561	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[11]	1600	✓	✓	✓		✓	
Indiv.	25	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	

Table 7. The results from the analysis of the networks for Poland

4.2.7 Switzerland

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs	10
Number of individual websites	9

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

- [1]. <http://www.observatoire-esspace.eu/>
- [2]. <http://www.sel-suisse.ch/>
- [3]. <http://www.acpch.ch/liens/>
- [4]. <http://www.decroissance-bern.ch/index.php>
- [5]. <https://radar.squat.net/en>
- [6]. <http://www.wbg-schweiz.ch/mitglieder.html>
- [7]. <http://www.apres-ge.ch>
- [8]. <http://www.lets.ch/links.php>
- [9]. <http://www.loconomie.ch>
- [10]. <http://www.ueca.ch>

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact	E-Mail	Description
[1]	674	✓	✓	✓	✓	
[2]	17	✓	✓	✓	✓	
[3]	30	✓	✓	✓	✓	
[4]	22	✓	✓			✓
[5]	40	✓	✓	✓	✓	
[6]	534	✓	✓	✓	✓	
[7]	149	✓	✓			✓
[8]	29	✓	✓	✓		
[9]	3	✓	✓			
[10]	27	✓	✓			
Indiv.	9	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 8. The results from the analysis of the networks for Switzerland

4.2.8 Italy

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs	7
Number of individual websites	42

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

- [1]. <http://www.economiasolidale.net>
- [2]. <http://www.retegas.org/>
- [3]. <http://www.retecosol.org/>
- [4]. <http://www.tempomat.it/>
- [5]. <http://www.abitarenellacrisi.org>
- [6]. <http://www.coworkingproject.com>
- [7]. <http://www.coworkingfor.com/>

- [8]. <http://www.associazionenazionalebdt.it/>
 [9]. <http://www.altromercato.it/it>
 [10]. <https://romattiva.wordpress.com/centrisocialiroma/>
 [11]. <http://www.bilancidigiustizia.it/>
 [12]. <http://www.cooperazione.net/>
 [13]. <http://www.punk4free.org/concerti/elenco-locali-e-centri-sociali.html>
 [14]. <http://cipsi.it/>
 [15]. <http://www.noprofit.org/>

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact	E-Mail	Description	Date	Zip/City
[1]	--							
[2]	1000	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
[3]	83	✓	✓			✓	✓	
[4]	132	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
[5]	26	✓	✓	✓	✓			
[6]	114	✓	✓					
[7]	209	✓	✓	✓		✓		
[8]	303	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓
[9]	7	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓
[10]	61	✓	✓	✓				
[11]	11	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
[12]	7	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
[13]	849	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓
[14]	23	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓
[15]	97	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
Indiv.	864	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		

Table 9. The results from the analysis of the networks for Italy

4.2.9 United Kingdom

Number of Hubs/Sub-hubs	15
Number of individual websites	5

The hubs/sub-hubs we analyzed are the following:

- [1]. <http://www.homelessuk.org/search/searchService.asp?ds=1>
 [2]. <http://www.self-help.org.uk/search/>
 [3]. <http://locality.org.uk/members/>
 [4]. <http://www.dtascot.org.uk/content/directory-of-members/directory>
 [5]. <http://www.dtawales.org.uk/by-name/>
 [6]. <http://www.uk.coop/directory/all>
 [7]. <http://buysocialdirectory.org.uk/directory>
 [8]. <http://www.mygreendirectory.info/listing/location/united-kingdom>
 [9]. <http://www.letslinkuk.net/regions/uk-map.htm>
 [10]. <http://www.communityshops.coop/shops>
 [11]. <http://animalrightsuk.org/localanimalrightsgroups.html>
 [12]. <http://www.transitionnetwork.org/initiatives/by-number>
 [13]. <http://www.globaljustice.org.uk/contact-local-group>

- [14]. <http://www.ethicalconsumer.org/boycotts/boycottlist.aspx>
 [15]. http://www.stonewall.org.uk/at_home/whats_in_my_area/default.asp

The results are the following:

Hub	Total Entries	Title	URL	Contact	E-Mail	Description	Date
[1]	7,243	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
[2]	2,227	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
[3]	700	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
[4]	230	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
[5]	40	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
[6]	12,717	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[7]	8,556	✓	✓	✓			
[8]	1858	✓	✓	✓		✓	
[9]	--						
[10]	336	✓	✓	✓			✓
[11]	101	✓	✓	✓	✓		
[12]	460	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
[13]	49	✓	✓	✓ (area)			
[14]	65	✓	✓			✓	
[15]	709	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Indiv.	5	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 10. The results from the analysis of the networks for UK

5 Documentation of the process

In this section we describe the process for analyzing the networks. For each network we describe the contents we analyzed, the actions we performed for reaching the actual content that was extracted, the information that we exported, the tools and methods we used, and the problems we have encountered.

5.1 Greek Networks

Greek Hub 1 (<http://www.enallaktikos.gr>)

The URL of the Greek network we analyzed is http://www.enallaktikos.gr/kg15el_diktya-allileggyis.html/. The following figure (Figure 1) shows a snapshot of the network. The area inside the red rectangle denotes the sites, which are categorized under various regions. After selecting a specific region the lists of sites that fall into this region are revealed. The information we analyzed from this hub contains the title, the URL of the site, and contact information (address, postal code, and city). In total 3357 sites were extracted.

The screenshot shows the website **enallaktikos.gr** with a navigation menu at the top: ΑΡΧΙΚΗ | ΔΙΚΤΥΑ ΑΛΛΗΛΕΓΓΥΗΣ | ΑΝΤΑΛΛΑΣΣΟΝΤΑΙ - ΧΑΡΙΖΟΝΤΑΙ | ΝΕΑ | ΑΡΘΡΟΓΡΑΦΙΑ | ΠΟΙΟΙ ΕΙΜΑΣΤΕ | ΕΠΙΚΟΙΝΩΝΙΑ.

The main content area is divided into three sections:

- ΑΝΑΖΗΤΗΣΤΕ ΚΟΙΝΩΝΙΚΟ ΔΙΚΤΥΟ**: A search interface with dropdown menus for 'Τύπος δικτύου', 'Περιφέρεια', 'Περιφερειακή Ενότητα', and 'Δήμος', followed by an 'Αναζήτηση' button.
- ΔΙΚΤΥΑ ΑΛΛΗΛΕΓΓΥΗΣ**: A list of mutual aid networks. A red box highlights the following entry:
 - Βρέθηκαν: 3374 δίκτυα
 - Αττικής
 - Κεντρικού Τομέα Αθηνών
 - Δήμος Αθηναίων [9186]
 - Σκόρος
 - Ερεσού και Ζωοδόχου Πηγής 63, Αθήνα 106 81, Ελλάδα
 - skoros@esrin.net Τηλ.: 6983 868344 (κατά τις ώρες λειτουργίας)
 - http://skoros.esrin.net/
 - Το Φασούλι
 - Αθήνα 105 55, Ελλάδα
 - http://fasouli.wordpress.com/
 - https://www.facebook.com/pages/Φασούλι/1667216409470360/?fbclid=...
- ΔΗΜΟΦΙΛΗ**: A section with a 'Σήμερα' (Today) tab and news items:
 - 5000 ευρώ πρόστιμο στην 5 χρόνια άνεργη Κυρία που τόλμησε να
 - ΔΠΡΕΑΝ download 394 βιβλίων τέχνης από το Μητροπολιτικό
 - ΟΑΕΔ: Όλες οι πληροφορίες για τις 19.460 θέσεις εργασίας με μισθό 750€
 - Σε αυτά τα κομμάτια μπορείτε να δωρίσετε τα μαλλιά σας για παιδιά

Figure 1. Snapshot from the Greek hub (<http://www.enallaktikos.gr>) with the information we extracted

Greek Hub 2 (<http://www.solidarity4all.gr/>)

The home page of the hub did not contain any links to particular sites. Therefore we clicked on “ΔΟΜΕΣ ΑΛΛΗΛΕΓΓΥΗΣ” and a list containing references to the particular websites revealed. The list is 10 pages long. After clicking a single result a new webpage showing more information about this site appeared. The following figure (Figure 2) shows an indicative screenshot of such a result. In the following picture we’ve marked using red rectangles the information we’ve extracted from these webpages.

Καταναλωτικός Συνεταιρισμός ΠΑΝΔΩΡΑ *title*
 Συνεταιρισμοί - Αλληλέγγυο Εμπόριο

ΠΑΡΟΥΣΙΑΣΗ ΤΗΣ ΔΟΜΗΣ

Είναι αλήθεια ότι, μια φορά κι' έναν καιρό, στην Ελλάδα, στην Πατρίδα μας, καλλιεργούσαμε τη γη μας, εκτρέφαμε τα ζώα μας και η χώρα όχι μόνο ζούσε αλλά έκανε και εξαγωγές. Σήμερα ούτε καλλιεργούμε ούτε παράγουμε, ζούμε με δανεικά και η χώρα έγινε αποικία χρέους, που σημαίνει φτώχεια, εξαθλίωση και ταπείνωση του ελληνικού λαού.

Αυτή την καταστροφή που ολοένα μεγαλώνεται θεωρούμε ότι, αν ενώσουμε τις όποιες δυνάμεις έχουμε ως πολίτες της χώρας, μπορούμε ειρηνικά να την αναστρέψουμε. Και ένας τρόπος που προτείνουμε, ρεαλιστικός και αναγκαίος, είναι η δημιουργία – σύσταση καταναλωτικών παραγωγικών συνεταιρισμών.

Στα πλαίσια ενός τέτοιου θεσμού τόσο ο καταναλωτής όσο και ο παραγωγός βγαίνουν κερδισμένοι αφού ο μεν καταναλωτής αγοράζει φθηνότερα ο δε παραγωγός πουλάει ακριβότερα και το επί πλέον κέρδος κοινωνικοποιείται προς όφελος της ελληνικής οικονομίας.

Με τέτοιους καταναλωτικούς παραγωγικούς συνεταιρισμούς θα ξαναζωντανέψει το κοινοτικό πνεύμα, που βοήθησε τον ελληνισμό να επιβιώσει ακόμα και τότε που βρέθηκε εθνικά υπόδουλος.

Όταν ο Ελληνικός λαός μπορεί με τη συμμετοχή του σ' ένα δίκτυο πολιτών να συμμετέχει ενεργά στη διαμόρφωση των βασικών αξιών της ζωής του και της κοινωνίας γενικότερα, τότε θα αλλάξουν πολλά πράγματα. Θα δημιουργήσουμε πλούτο

ΦΩΤΟΓΡΑΦΙΕΣ (2)

contact info

ΣΤΟΙΧΕΙΑ ΕΠΙΚΟΙΝΩΝΙΑΣ
 Αγίου Ιωάννου 24Γ, ΑΓΙΑ ΠΑΡΑΣΚΕΥΗ,
 Δήμος Αγίας Παρασκευής
 Τηλ: 210 6000078

e-mail synpandora@gmail.com
website <http://www.synpandora.gr/>

Figure 2. Snapshot from the Greek hub (<http://www.solidarity4all.gr/>) with the information we extracted

The information contained: (a) the title of the website, (b) the URL of the homepage, (c) the contact information (address, phone number) and (d) the contact e-mail address. We followed this process for all the results. The analysis revealed 380 websites.

Greek Hub 3 (<http://omikronproject.gr/>)

The home page of the hub did not contain any links to particular sites. Therefore we clicked on “OUR PRODUCTIONS” and then on “Map of glassroots groups in Greece (2nd edition)”. In that web page we could find a list containing references to the particular websites. In the following figure (Figure 3) we’ve marked using red rectangles the information we’ve extracted from the webpage. The information contained 379 results with their title, their URL and the category they fall into.

Alternative Economies and Local Exchange Trading Systems *Category*
Movements organising micro-economies without middle-men or without money, to increase solidarity and strengthen social bonds

Links- Title

- [7 Strofes](#)
- [60 Lepta](#)
- [Aftarkeia](#)
- [Aftonomo Steki](#)
- [Agronaftes](#)
- [Agrotiko Pantopoleio Kalamarias](#) [Agricultural grocery shop of Kalamaria]
- [Agrotopia](#)
- [Aneksartiti Protovoulia Politon Dimou Thermaikou](#) [Independent initiative of the citizens of Thermaikos]
- [Anoixto Diktyo](#) [Open Network]
- [Antallaktiko Diktyo Kalymnos](#) [Exchange network of Kalymnos]
- [Antallaktiki Oikonomia](#) [Exchange Economy]
- [Antallaktiko Veroia](#) [Exchange Veroia]
- [Antallazo](#)
- [Artemida-Spata D.K.A.](#)
- [BABY feat](#)
- [Bios Co-op](#)
- [Boutsouni](#)
- [Chania Net Exchange](#)
- [DARETH](#)
- [DIALAS](#)
- [Diktyo Allilegiis Dionysou](#) [Network of Solidarity of Dionysos]
- [Diktyo Allilegiis Zwgrafoi](#) [Network of Solidarity of Zwgrafoi]
- [Diktyo Antallagis Ag. Paraskevis](#) [Network of exchange of Agia Paraskevi]

Figure 3. Snapshot from the Greek hub (<http://omikronproject.gr/>) with the information we extracted

Greek Hub 4 (<http://www.boroume.gr/>)

After visiting the hub <http://www.boroume.gr> we clicked on “Δίκτυο” and then on “Ποιους Βοηθάμε”. This led us to a new web page (<http://www.boroume.gr/poious-voithame/>) containing four different categories. Each category contained a list of websites. The following figure (Figure 4) shows a snapshot from the category “Ιδρύματα”.

Figure 4. Snapshot from the Greek hub (<http://www.boroume.gr/>)

Each result contained some information about the site, however after clicking on the link “περισσότερα”, more information was revealed. Figure 5 shows an indicative screenshot of such a website. The information we extracted from these websites contained: (a) the title, (b) contact information (address, postal code, and phone numbers), (c) e-mail address, (d) the website URL and (e) a short description. The total number of results we have extracted from this hub are 656.

Title Σύλλογος Γονέων και Κηδεμόνων Νοητικά Στερούμενων Ατόμων "Οι Άγιοι Ανάργυροι"

Contact Info Αγίων Αναργύρων 1, 153 51, Κάντζα Παλλήνης | 210 6667180, 210 6667189 | info@ag-anargyroi.gr **e-mail**

Website URL www.ag-anargyroi.gr

Description Ο Σύλλογος ξεκίνησε το 1983 από 38 οικογενειών νοητικά υστερούντων ατόμων, που είχαν την αγωνία τι θα γίνουν τα παιδιά τους στο μέλλον. Με αυτό το σκεπτικό, δημιούργησαν το δικό τους οικοτροφείο, όπου ξεκίνησε να λειτουργεί το 1997. Σήμερα στο Σύλλογο Γονέων και Κηδεμόνων Νοητικά Υστερούντων Ατόμων "ΟΙ ΑΓΙΟΙ ΑΝΑΡΓΥΡΟΙ" μετέχουν 52 οικογένειες για τον αντίστοιχο αριθμό περιθαλπομένων ατόμων. Σε καθημερινή βάση παρέχεται ατομικό και ομαδικό πρόγραμμα από ειδικούς παιδαγωγούς, προσαρμοσμένο στις ιδιαιτερότητες, τις ειδικές ανάγκες και ικανότητες που διαθέτουν τα παιδιά, ώστε να βελτιώνουν το επίπεδο αυτοεμπνεύσεως.

Σχετικά άρθρα :

>> Οι ανάγκες 52 παιδιών με νοητική υστέρηση στο οικοτροφείο "Οι Αγ. Ανάργυροι" | Φεβρουάριος 2013

Figure 5. Snapshot from the Greek hub (<http://www.boroume.gr/>) with the information we extracted

5.2 Swedish Networks

Swedish Hub 1 (<http://www.volontarbyran.org/for-organisationer/>)

The following figure (Figure 6) shows a screenshot of the home page of the network. In the lower right part of the figure (in the red rectangle) there is a section entitled “Ideella organisationer”. This section has a drop down list containing all the organizations. After selecting a specific organization, and after clicking the link “Visa fullständig beskrivning >>” its corresponding information are shown.

The screenshot shows the homepage of the Swedish Hub website. The main navigation bar includes 'Start', 'För volontärer', 'För organisationer', 'Utbildning', 'Företag', 'Frågor & svar', and 'Om Volontärbyrån'. The 'För organisationer' tab is active. The page title is 'Volontärbyrån hjälper er att hitta frivilliga'. The main content area is divided into several sections: 'Våra fem bästa tips för att rekrytera frivilliga', 'Vi kan ideellt engagemang', 'Utbilda dig hos oss', 'Din kunskapskälla', 'Nyhetsbrev', and 'Forums omvärldsbevakning'. A red rectangle highlights the 'Ideella organisationer' section, which contains a dropdown menu labeled 'Välj organisation'.

Figure 6. Snapshot from the Swedish hub (<http://www.volontarbyran.org/for-organisationer/>)

The information we exported (and are shown in Figure 7) is: (a) the title, (b) the contact information (address, postal code, city, and phone number), (c) the e-mail address, (d) a short description and (e) the website URL. The total number of organizations we found for this hub are 2082.

Ideella organisationer	
Här hittar ni samtliga organisationer som registrerat uppdrag på Volontärbyrån.	
Title	1,6 & 2,6 miljonerklubben <small>visa organisationens uppdrag</small>
Contact Info	1,6 & 2,6 miljonerklubben Grev Turegatan 27 114 38 Stockholm
	Orgnr: 802407-8779
Description	Beskrivning: Vi vill att alla kvinnor ska ha bästa tänkbara livskvalitet och hälsa! Vår inre och vår yttre hälsa hör ihop därför arbetar vi holistiskt och tar upp alla aspekter av hälsa. Mat, motion, kultur och gemenskap. Vi förmedlar kunskap om hjärt- och kärlsjukdomar och andra sjukdomar som drabbar kvinnor. Vi arrangerar också en mängd spännande och roliga aktiviteter. Namnet kommer av att det fanns 1,6 miljoner kvinnor över 45 år i Sverige när föreningen grundades
Contact Info	Telefon: 08-20 51 59
e-mail	info@1.6miljonerklubben.com
Website URL	Hemsida: www.1.6miljonerklubben.com

Figure 7. Snapshot from the Swedish hub ([http:// www.volontarbyran.org/for-organisationer/](http://www.volontarbyran.org/for-organisationer/)) with the information we extracted

Swedish Hub 2 (<http://vuxnabarn.nu/forum/stodgrupper-f56/sjalvhjelpsgrupper-och-samtalsgrupper-sverige-t4488.html>)

The above URL points to a specific thread of a user's forum (shown in Figure 8). There are several URLs among the posts of the forum. Unfortunately the only way to retrieve the required information is to visit the aforementioned URLs and extract those information. However every site has a different structure and therefore we cannot use a common method for extracting particular information from them. So, we automatically extracted all the URLs that could be found in the given thread and then we analyzed the contents of these URLs manually. The total number of the extracted results are 88 and the results we extracted for these organizations are: (a) title, (b) URL of the website, (c) contact information (with address, city, postal code and telephone numbers), (d) e-mail address and (e) the dates that the identified organizations has been active.

BESVARA ↵
3 inlägg • Sida 1 av 1

☆ Självhjälpsgrupper och samtalsgrupper i Sverige

Dav SvartaKatten » mån 03 sep 2012, 04:24
 En rejäl sökning på internet har givit att dessa organisationer och föreningar erbjuder hjälp eller stöd med uppstart av självhjälpsgrupper, eller driver redan självhjälpsgrupper i någon form. Jag har även tagit med föreningar som inriktar sig på olika psykiska sjukdomar, missbruksproblem, ensamstående föräldrar, självmord, mobbing, hedersvåld, med mera med mera, eftersom människor kan ha blandade typer av problem. Även samtalsgrupper för barn är med.

Jag garanterar inte att föreningarna/organisationerna uppfyller vad dom lovar på sina hemsidor. Jag bara länkar och tipsar.

Tipsa gärna om organisationer som inte finns med genom att svara på tråden så lägger jag till dem i listan!

Sidor med samlad info om självhjälp

Drugsmart.com
 Drugsmart.com är Sveriges största ungdomssajt om alkohol och andra droger. Här hittar du kontaktuppgifter till en rad olika stödgruppsverksamheter runt om i landet. Klicka på kartan eller på länkarna till höger för att få reda på vilken verksamhet som finns närmast dig.
Nyckelord: missbruk, ungdom

Kuling.nu
 Mötesplatsen för dig som har en förälder med psykisk sjukdom. Här finns information om vart Du kan vända Dig när Du behöver hjälp. De flesta behöver stöd när en förälder har psykiska problem. På många platser i landet har man grupper för barn och ungdom där man kan få hjälp. I grupperna träffar man andra som också har en förälder med psykisk sjukdom, får kunskap om psykiska sjukdomar och kan få hjälp att hitta det stöd man behöver för sin egen person.
Nyckelord: psykisk sjukdom, dysfunktionella familjer, barn, ungdom

SvartaKatten
 Global Moderator
 Moderator
TRÅDSTARTARE

Trådstartare
 Inlägg: 11978
 Blev medlem: sön 30 sep 2007, 23:58
 Ort: Östan om sol och västan om måne
 Blogg: [Visa blogg \(12\)](#)
 Roll: Global moderator och Administratör, samt dissociativt minnesstörd så in i bomben.

Figure 8. Snapshot from the Swedish hub (<http://vuxnabarn.nu/forum/stodgrupper-f56/sjalvhjalsgrupper-och-samtalsgrupper-sverige-t4488.html>) with the information we extracted

Swedish Individual Websites

The list of individual websites has been analyzed manually. This means that we extracted manually information about the corresponding organizations after visiting them in a web browser. The analysis of the individual websites revealed 16 organizations and we extracted the following information: (a) the title, (b) the website URL, (c) contact information including address, postal code and telephone numbers, (d) e-mail address and (e) the dates that the organization has been active.

The only problem we faced with the individual websites is that we could not analyze the website <http://www.skankes.se/> because it no longer exists.

5.3 German Networks

German Hub 1 (<http://www.solidarische-oekonomie.de>)

Figure 9 shows a snapshot of the homepage of the hub. To reveal the list of organizations we hovered over the menu bar and found under “Formen und Beispiele” and then “Projekte hierzulande”. This revealed a list of categories and each category contained the lists of organizations. We extracted the following information for each organization: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (address, postal code and telephone numbers), (d) e-mail address and (e) the dates that the organization has been active. The total number of results we identified for the hub is 578.

Figure 9. Snapshot from the German hub (<http://www.solidarische-oekonomie.de>) with the information we extracted

German Hub 2 (<http://www.mondamo.de/linklist/>)

Figure 10 shows a snapshot of the homepage of the hub. The red rectangle shows the list of organizations that we have extracted. In addition each organization is an internal link that leads to a webpage for that organization. This internal webpage contains some more information about the organization. The red rectangle in Figure 11 shows the information we have extracted from these internal webpages. We extracted the following information for each organization: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (only the city), and (d) a short description. The total number of results we identified for the hub is 158.

Figure 10. Snapshot from the German hub (<http://www.mondamo.de/linklist/>) with the information we extracted

Figure 11. Snapshot from the German hub (<http://www.mondamo.de/linklist/>) with the information we extracted

German Hub 3 (<http://www.friedenskooperative.de/netzwerk/links-hr.htm>)

Figure 12 shows a snapshot of the homepage of the hub. The red rectangle shows the list of organizations that we have extracted with the information they contain. We extracted the following information for each organization: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (address, postal code, telephone and fax numbers), and (d) e-mail address. The total number of results we identified for the hub is 58.

Figure 12. Snapshot from the German hub (<http://www.friedenskooperative.de/netzwerk/links-hr.htm>) with the information we extracted

German Hub 4 (<http://www.tauschringportal.de/>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any organizations. After clicking on the link with title “TauschRing-Linkliste” (shown in the left red rectangle of Figure 13) a list of organizations revealed (shown in the right red rectangle of Figure 13). We extracted the following information for each organization: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (only city), and (d) date. The total number of results we identified for the hub is 368.

NAME	PLZ	ORT	Geprüft
PLZ 0			
15 Tauschringe, davon 1 gestorben		und 8 mit aktivem Link	
tauschring Dresden e.V.	01067	Dresden	02.12.2012
tauschring Dresden Studenwerk	01069	Dresden	02.12.2012
tauschbörse Dresden-Prohlis	01239	Dresden	02.12.2012
Coswiger Tauschring	01640	Coswig	02.12.2012
TRX-ZeitTauschring	01809	Heidenau	02.12.2012
talente-Tausch-Ring Zittau	02763	Zittau	02.12.2012
tauschring "SpinnNetz"	02943	Weißwasser	
atzen Tauschring Leipzig e.V.	04162	Leipzig	02.12.2012
Dessauer Tauschring	06844	Dessau	02.12.2012
Elstertaler Tauschring	07545	Gera	
tauschring Jena	07743	Jena	02.12.2012
tauschring Vogtland	08468	Reichenbach	gestorben 31.12.2007
talentbörse Plauen/Vogtland	08523	Plauen	28.05.2009
tauschkreis-Chemnitz	09112	Chemnitz	
Freiberger Tauschring	09599	Freiberg	02.12.2012
PLZ 1			
46 Tauschringe		18 mit aktivem Link	
tauschring Teutoburger Platz	10119	Berlin	
riedrichshainer Tauschring	10245	Berlin	02.12.2012
auschnetz Lichtenberg	10365	Berlin	02.12.2012
tauschring Prenzlauer Berg	10437	Berlin	02.12.2012
tauschring Prenzlauer Berg	10437	Berlin	02.12.2012

Figure 13. Snapshot from the German hub (<http://www.tauschringportal.de/>) with the information we extracted

German Hub 5 (<http://www.umsonstladen.de/>)

Figure 14 shows the homepage of the hub. The red rectangle shows the list of organizations we found and the information we extracted for them. More specifically we extracted the following information for each organization: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (address, postal code and telephone number). The total number of results we identified for the hub is 92.

Werkstatt <http://www.ak-loek.de/Main/Fahrradwerkstatt> und die Freie Uni Hamburg, in der sich Menschen in kleinen Lerngruppen an Werkstatt, in der sich Aktive gegenseitig Reparaturfähigkeiten beibringen und NutzerInnen gegen eine Spende bei konkreten Reparaturen

Die Wiener Gruppe W.E.G. bietet auf ihrer Website Raum für einen Ressourcenpool, der die Möglichkeiten des **KostNixLadens** erweitert diese sind aber nicht in weitergehende Projekte eingebunden.

Adressen in Deutschland

Baden-Württemberg

- **Umsonstladen Heidelberg**
 - immer jeden 1. & 3. Samstag auf dem Wilhelmsplatz in der Weststadt
 - Öffnung: Sa, 10.00 bis 14.00 Uhr
 - <https://umsonstladenheidelberg.wordpress.com/>
- **Umsonstladen Tübingen**
 - Ludvigstr. 15, 72072 Tübingen
 - Öffnung: Do, 18 bis 21 Uhr und So, 15 bis 18 Uhr
 - <http://lu15.de/umsonstladen/>
 - Schellingstr. 6, 72072 Tübingen
 - Öffnung: Mi, 16 bis 23 Uhr und Sa, 12 bis 19 Uhr.
 - <http://www.schellingstrasse.de/index.php?id=436>
- **Umsonstladen Reutlingen**
 - in der Kulturschock Zelle, Albstr. 78, 72764 Reutlingen
 - Öffnung: während Veranstaltungen bis 24 Uhr
- **Umsonstladen Karlsruhe**
 - Im Aufbau, Anschrift wird noch bekannt gegeben
 - Mitstreiter gesucht!!!
 - <http://www.schenk-raum.de>
- **Umsonstladen Freiburg**
 - Basler Str. 103 (KTS), 79100 Freiburg i. Br.
 - Öffnung: Di, + Do, 17 bis 19 Uhr
 - <http://www.kts-freiburg.org/spip/spip.php?article178>
- **Umsonstladen Schopfheim**
 - im Café Irrlicht, Bahnhofstr. 3, 79650 Schopfheim
 - Öffnung:
 - Tel.: 07622 - 5657
 - <http://www.irrlicht.org>

Bayern

- **Mosaik Bamberg - Umsonstladen und Begegnungsstätte**

Figure 14. Snapshot from the German hub (<http://www.umsonstladen.de/>) with the information we extracted

German Hub 6 (<http://www.syndikat.org/de/links/>)

Figure 15 shows the homepage of the hub. The red rectangle shows the list of organizations we found and the information we extracted for them. More specifically we extracted the following information for each organization: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (address, postal code and telephone number). The total number of results we identified for the hub is 27.

Syndikat Projekte Regionales Veröffentlichungen mehr Infos Mitmachen Kontakt

Startseite · Links

Links

Hier suchen...

Selbstorganisierte Hausprojekte (nach PLZ)

- Kellnerstraße e.V. 06110 **Halle** Selbstverwaltetes Hausprojekt mit Infoladen
- Regenbogenfabrik Block 109 e. V. 10959 **Berlin**
- Wohnen, Leben und Arbeiten, Kultur und Ökologie
- Yorkstraße 59 10999 **Berlin** NewYork im Bethanien
- KuBiZ 13088 **Berlin** Weissensee
- Gutshauskollektiv Friedrichhof 13 17349 **Kublank**
- Ökozentrum 27283 **Verden**
- Trike Wohnen e.G. 31139 **Hildesheim** Selbstverwaltetes Wohnprojekt
- Kommune Niederkaufrungen 34260 **Kaufrungen**
- SSK Salierring Köln 50677 **Köln**
- SSM Sozialistische Selbsthilfe Mülheim Selbstverwaltetes Wohn- und Arbeitsprojekt 51063 **Köln**
- MiKa e.G. MieterInneninitiative **Karlsruhe** Wohnungsgenossenschaft e.G.
- Gemeinschaftsorientiertes Wohnen und Leben in den ehemaligen "Smiley-Barracks" in 76149 **Karlsruhe**
- Neuwerk e.G. Selbstverwaltetes, genossenschaftliches Projekt in 78467 **Konstanz**
- Gewerbe, Handwerk & Kultur unter einem Dach
- Kommune Waltershausen 99880 **Waltershausen**
- planet10 Pernerstorfergasse 121100 **Wien**

Organisationen, die selbstorganisierte Hausprojekte unterstützen (alphabetisch)

- Die Bewegungsstiftung 27283 **Verden** Anstöße für soziale Bewegungen
Tel.: (04231) 957540, Fax: (04231) 957541 info@bewegungsstiftung.de
- Forum Gemeinschaftliches Wohnen e. V. **Hannover** mit Projektbörse
Zusammenschluss von Vereinen und Einzelpersonen, die gemeinschaftliche, generationsübergreifende Wohnformen bekannt machen, initiieren und verwirklichen
- GeWo-Netz Netzwerk gemeinschaftliches Wohnen **Freiburg**
- STAITBAU **Hamburg** berät und betreut Menschen, die nachbarschaftlich zusammenwohnen und ihre Häuser gemeinschaftlich verwalten
- Projektwerkstatt auf Gegenseitigkeit Ruhlsdorfer Straße 18 16359 **Biesenthal** Tel.: (03337)

Ausgewählte Termine

Samstag 10.10.15
Mitgliederversammlung Freiburg

Samstag 13.06.15
Mitgliederversammlung Gersdorf

Weitere Termine

Figure 15. Snapshot from the German hub (<http://www.syndikat.org/de/links/>) with the information we extracted

German Hub 7 (http://konsumpf.de/?page_id=39)

Figure 16 shows the homepage of the hub. The red rectangle shows the list of organizations we found and the information we extracted for them. More specifically we extracted the following information for each organization: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (address, postal code and telephone number). The total number of results we identified for the hub is 27.

Figure 16. Snapshot from the German hub (http://konsumpf.de/?page_id=39) with the information we extracted

German Hub 8 (<http://www.tafel.de/die-tafeln/tafel-suche/adressenliste.html>)

The homepage of the hub contains a list of organizations splitted in 38 pages. The red rectangle in Figure 17 shows the organizations and the information we extracted for them. We found 947 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information and (d) e-mail address.

DIE TAFELN
Essen, wo es hingehört

Sie sind hier: [Startseite](#) » [Die Tafeln](#) » [Tafel-Suche](#) » [Adressenliste](#)

Die Tafeln

Sortieren nach: [Name der Tafel](#) | [PLZ](#) | [Ort](#)

Ergebnisse 1 bis 25 von 947

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24
25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32 33 34 35 36 37 38 >

Aachener Tafel e.V.
Clermontstraße 10
52066 Aachen
Bundesland: Nordrhein-Westfalen
Ansprechpartner: Jutta Schlockermann
Telefon: 0241 - 9977474
Fax: 0241 - 9128204
E-Mail: info@aachener-tafel.de
Website: www.aachener-tafel.de

Aalener Tafel - Kocherladen e.V.
Bahnhofstr. 55
73430 Aalen
Bundesland: Baden-Württemberg
Ansprechpartner: Gerhard Vietz
Telefon: 07361 - 680069
Fax: 07361 - 55133
E-Mail: kocherladen@web.de
Website: www.evangelische-kirchengemeinde-aalen.de/html/kocherladen_e_v_.html

Abensberger Tafel e.V.
1 Bad Gögginger Weg 22
93326 Abensberg
Bundesland: Bayern
Ansprechpartner: Rudolf Buchner
Telefon: 09443 - 1522
Fax: 09443 - 992824
E-Mail: rudolf.buchner@me.com
Website: <http://www.abensberg-tafel.de>

Figure 17. Snapshot from the German hub (<http://www.tafeln.de/die-tafeln/tafel-suche/adressenliste.html>) with the information we extracted

German Hub 9

(<http://www.arbeitslosenverband.org/mitgliedsverbaende/index.html>)

The homepage of the hub contains a list of 5 organizations (which can also be found after clicking “Mitgliedsverbände” on the menu on the left of the webpage). The red rectangle in Figure 18 shows the organizations and the information we extracted for them. As already mentioned, we found 5 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, and (c) contact information.

Sie sind hier: Startseite / Mitgliedsverbände

Arbeitslosenverband Deutschland Bundesverband e.V.

DER PARITÄTISCHE
UNSER SPITZENVERBAND

Mitgliedsverbände

Startseite	
Leitsätze	
Satzung	
Mitgliedsverbände	
Vorstand	
Archiv	
Impressum	
Kontakt	

Landesverband Berlin
Franz-Jacob-Straße 20
10369 Berlin

Landesverband Brandenburg
Bahnhofstr. 1A
14774 Brandenburg an der Havel

Landesverband Mecklenburg Vorpommern
Perleberger Straße 22 (Haus der Begegnung)
19063 Schwerin

Thüringer Arbeitslosenverband
Brühl 8-16
99423 Weimar

ALV Bildungswerk Brandenburg
Asta-Nielsen-Str. 3
14480 Potsdam

Aktuelles

Statement des Arbeitslosenverbandes zum 4. Armuts- und Reichtumsbericht Armuts- und Reichtumsbericht veröffentlicht Aktionstag "umfairteilen" am 13.04.2013 Bündnis für ein menschenwürdiges Existenzminimum Bildgalerie umfairteilen DEMO 29.09.2012

UM fair TEILEN
Reich Mann besteuere

Bündnis für ein menschenwürdiges Existenzminimum

Website powered by weblica

Figure 18. Snapshot from the German hub (<http://www.arbeitslosenverband.org/mitgliedsverbaende/index.html>) with the information we extracted

German Hub 10 (<http://medibueros.m-bient.com/standorte.html>)

The homepage of the hub contains an interactive map with the locations of the organizations that are listed. Just below the map there is the list of organizations with various information about them (shown in the red rectangle of Figure 19). We found 34 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, (d) e-mail address, and (e) the city where each organization is located.

Figure 19. Snapshot from the German hub (<http://medibueros.m-bient.com/standorte.html>) with the information we extracted

German Hub 11 (<http://www.evangelische-obdachlosenhilfe.de/index.php/mitglieder.html>)

The homepage of the hub contains list of organizations (which can also be found after clicking “Mitglieder” on the menu on the left of the webpage). Figure 20 shows the organizations with the information we extracted for them. We found 75 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, and (d) e-mail address.

Evangelische Obdachlosenhilfe in Deutschland e.V. A : A : A Kontakt Impressum

Seite Aktuelles Info Recht Publikationen Newsletter

Sie befinden sich hier:
www.evangelische-obdachlosenhilfe.de Info Mitglieder

Vorlesen

Die Mitglieder

Auf dieser Seite erhalten Sie einen Überblick über die Mitglieder der Evangelischen Obdachlosenhilfe in Deutschland e.V. Geordnet nach Orten

Stiftung Hamburger Arbeiter-Kolonie

Schäferhofweg 30
 25482 Appen
 Tel.: (04101) 50060
info@schaeferhof-sh.de

Bodelschwingh-Haus Augsburg

Inneres Pfaffengäßchen 14
 86152 Augsburg
 Tel.: (0821) 45019-3331
eckart.h@diakonie-augsburg.de

Wohnungslosenhilfe keuznacher diakonie

Waldemarstr. 26
 55543 Bad Kreuznach
 Tel.: (0671) 8394-933
frieder.zimmermann@kreuznacherdiakonie.de

Figure 20. Snapshot from the German hub (<http://www.evangelische-obdachlosenhilfe.de/index.php/mitglieder.html>) with the information we extracted

5.4 French Networks

French Hub 1 (<https://www.colibris-lemouvement.org/colibris>,
<http://colibris.ning.com/groups>)

The website of the hub contained an interactive map (shown in Figure 21). The user has to click several times (2-3) to limit the number of the results that are shown. After that a list with some results for the selected area were shown and the user could click on them and see more information about them. However this is a process that could not be performed in an automatic manner. Furthermore the website was only accessible using Internet Explorer. For these reasons we couldn't analyse these information from that hub.

Figure 21. Snapshot from the French hub (<https://www.colibris-lemouvement.org/colibris>) with the information we extracted

However after exploring the website we found a list of organizations after following the particular links; at first we click on the menu bar at the item with title “ENSEMBLE” then we selected on “Rejoindre un groupe local” and then we clicked on the link that has the following text “dans cette liste, à télécharger”. This revealed a list of organizations in a pdf file containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (the corresponding person only) and (d) e-mail address. The total number of results from the analysis of the above URL revealed 52 organizations.

Apart from the above and after a recommendation of the French team of the LiveWHAT project we analyzed the contents of the hub that can be found at <http://colibris.ning.com/groups>. Figure 22 shows the homepage of the hub; the red rectangle shows the list of organization that we analyzed. After clicking on a particular organization an internal webpage opened containing the information we extracted (shown in Figure 23). We extracted the following information from this hub: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) a short description, and (d) contact information (only the city). The total number of organizations we extracted for this hub is 468.

The screenshot shows the Colibris website interface. At the top, the logo 'colibris faire sa part' is on the left, and 'Le réseau social des colibris' with the tagline 'SE RENCONTRER • ÉCHANGER • S'ENTRAIDER' is on the right. A navigation bar includes links like ACCUEIL, MA PAGE, MEMBRES, AGENDA, FORUM, BLOGS, GROUPEs, PHOTO / VIDÉO, AIDE, and ACCÈS AU SITE COLIBRIS. Below the navigation, there's a section for 'Groupes locaux Colibris' with four featured groups: 'Une (R)évolution intérieure DES COLIBRIS' (148 membres), 'Colibris 30 Usage' (25 membres), 'Colibris 30 Nîmes' (77 membres), and 'Colibris Lorient 56 LORIENT' (97 membres). A sidebar on the right contains a welcome message, a sign-in section, and event listings. The main content area, titled 'Tous les groupes (485)', lists various groups. One group, 'Perma Colibris Aisne', is highlighted with a red box. Its details include 6 members, activity on June 2nd, and a focus on 'Permaculture & Apiculture'.

Figure 22. Snapshot from the French hub (<http://colibris.ning.com/groups>)

This screenshot shows the detailed page for the 'Perma Colibris Aisne' group. The title 'Perma Colibris Aisne' is highlighted in red. Below it, the creator 'Créé par Damien Paris' and a link 'Afficher les groupes' are visible. The 'INFORMATIONS' section features a circular diagram with 'Perma' at the center, surrounded by 'Wooding', 'Apiculture', 'Permaculture', 'Design', 'Stages', and 'Partage'. The 'Description' section, also highlighted in red, describes the group as 'Association Perm'api Permaculture & Apiculture' and provides details about its location in Aisne (02) near Jumencourt. The 'Website URL' is 'http://www.permapi.fr' and the 'Emplacement' is 'Jumencourt'. The 'Contact Info' section shows 6 members and activity on June 2nd. Social sharing options for Facebook and Twitter are also present.

Figure 23. Snapshot from the French hub (<http://colibris.ning.com/groups>) with the information we extracted

French Hub 2 (<http://mouves.org/>)

The homepage of the specific hub did not contain any list of organizations that could be exploited. After a recommendation of the French team of LiveWHAT project, we found lists of organizations in the following URLs (in the parenthesis we describe how to reach these URLs from the homepage of the hub):

- <http://mouves.org/le-mouves/les-partenaires-du-mouves> (clicked on “Le Mouves” and then on “Nos partenaires”)
- <http://mouves.org/le-mouves/les-membres-du-mouves/portraits-entrepreneurs-sociaux> (click on “Le Mouves” then on “Nos Membres” and finally on “Portraits d’entrepreneurs sociaux”)
- <http://mouves.org/le-mouves/gouvernance> (clicked on “Le Mouves” and then on “Notre organisation”)

Figure 24 shows an indicative screenshot of the first URL. In total we found 36 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL and a (c) a short description.

The screenshot shows the 'Nos partenaires' page on the Mouves website. The page title is 'Nos partenaires' and the breadcrumb is 'Accueil > Le Mouves et sa vision > Nos partenaires'. The main content is under the heading 'Les grands partenaires'. A table entry for 'La Caisse d'Epargne' is highlighted with red boxes. The table has three columns: 'Title', 'Description', and 'Website URL'. The 'Title' column contains 'La Caisse d'Epargne'. The 'Description' column contains a paragraph about the Caisse d'Epargne group. The 'Website URL' column contains a link 'Accédez au site de la Caisse d'Epargne'. The page also features a search bar, a newsletter sign-up form, and social media links.

Title	Description	Website URL
La Caisse d'Epargne	Fortes de l'appui et de la puissance financière du groupe BPCE, deuxième groupe bancaire en France, les Caisses d'Epargnes sont composées de 17 Banques Régionales. Ces banques sont solidement implantées au cœur de leur région tant par leur connaissance pointue des besoins du territoire couvert que par leur rôle d'acteur économique. La Caisse d'Epargne accompagne l'ensemble des décideurs qui impulsent l'économie régionale : entreprises, structures de l'économie sociale, organismes du logement social et de l'économie mixte, acteurs du secteur public et de l'immobilier professionnel. Elle dispose de 110 centres d'affaires et s'appuie sur l'expertise de chargés d'affaires spécialisés par secteur d'activité. Ils connaissent les particularités juridiques, réglementaires, fiscales et financières de ces secteurs et s'appuient également sur des experts en solutions spécifiques (crédit-bail, affacturage, cash-pooling...). Les réponses de la Caisse d'Epargne s'adapte à l'ensemble de la palette des besoins : de la demande de crédit à l'optimisation de la gestion quotidienne des flux et placements, jusqu'à une offre complète en ingénierie sociale. La Caisse d'Epargne conduit une politique de partenariats engagés avec les grandes fédérations de l'économie sociale, fidèle en cela à ses valeurs coopératives.	Accédez au site de la Caisse d'Epargne

Figure 24. Snapshot from the French hub (<http://mouves.org/le-mouves/les-partenaires-du-mouves>) with the information we extracted

French Hub 3 (<http://www.portail-solidarite.org/domaines/economie-sociale-et-solidaire>)

The homepage of the specific hub did not contain any list of organizations that could be exploited. The only information that existed is a scrolling banner on the bottom of the website (see Figure 25), that contained information about organizations; however such

information could not be extracted automatically, because some of these website were irrelevant or did not contain the required information, and for others it was not clear which information to extract.

Figure 25. Snapshot from the French hub (<http://www.portail-solidarite.org/domaines/economie-sociale-et-solidaire>) with links to other websites that contain information about organizations

After a recommendation of the French team of the LiveWHAT project, there was a different place in the hub to search for organizations. To find them we should click on “Acteurs” and then on “Fondations”. On the bottom of that page there was a link the website <http://www.centre-francais-fondations.org>. After that we clicked on “FONDATIONS & FONDS DE DOTATION” and then on “Annuaire” and we found a list of organizations. Each organization has a link that points to an internal web page containing particular information about the organization. Figure 26 shows an indicative screenshot of such a web page, and in red rectangles the information we extracted.

Figure 26. Snapshot from the French hub (<http://www.centre-francais-fondations.org>) with the information we extracted

The total number of organizations that we extracted is 297, and they contain the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (including address, postal code, and city), (d) e-mail address, (e) a short description and (f) the date of the creation of the organization.

French Hub 4 (<http://www.lelabo-ess.org/>)

The homepage of the specific hub did not contain any list of organizations that could be exploited. The French team of LiveWHAT project, informed us that we could use the document found in <https://www.francebarter.coop/GUIDE-PRATIQUE-BARTER-echanges-inter-entreprises.pdf>. In pages 27 and 28 we could find a list of organizations with some information about them. We found information for 105 organizations containing information about: (a) the title, (b) contact information (containing information only about the area), (c) a short description and (d) a date.

French Hub 5 (<http://www.unaf.fr/spip.php?rubrique3>)

The website of the hub contained a list of organizations that were sorted in alphabetical order. Each organization has a link that refers to a web page containing more information about the organization. Figure 27 shows an indicative screenshot of such web pages with the information we extracted for those. In total we extracted information about 62 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (containing address, postal code, and telephone and fax numbers), (d) e-mail address, (e) a short description and (f) a creation date.

The screenshot shows a web page for the 'Association des Collectifs Enfants Parents Professionnels' (ACEPP). The page is titled 'Associations membres' and has a sub-header 'Association des Collectifs Enfants Parents Professionnels'. The page is dated 'Fiche mise à jour le 01/08/2005'. The main content area is divided into several sections, each highlighted with a red box and labeled with a red text annotation:

- Title:** Association des Collectifs Enfants Parents Professionnels
- Contact info:** Association des Collectifs Enfants Parents Professionnels, Acepp, 29, rue du Charolais, 75012 Paris, Tél. : 01 44 73 85 20, Fax : 01 44 73 85 39
- e-mail:** info@acepp.asso.fr
- Website URL:** http://www.acepp.asso.fr
- Creation date:** Date de création : 1980
- Description:** Buts du Mouvement: La promotion, selon les statuts et la "Charte pour l'accueil de l'enfant" :
 - ▶ de la reconnaissance du parent comme premier éducateur de l'enfant,
 - ▶ de la place des parents dans tous les lieux d'accueil de l'enfant,
 - ▶ de la qualité de l'intervention éducative auprès des enfants dans un projet conjoint parents-professionnels,
 - ▶ du respect de la diversité culturelle et sociale des familles,
 - ▶ de réponses aux besoins des familles par des services de proximité évolutifs et innovants,
 - ▶ du soutien aux dynamiques collectives et citoyennes dans la vie locale,
 - ▶ des dispositifs de formation à la responsabilité associative pour les parents et de qualification et formation aux métiers de la petite enfance pour les professionnels.

Figure 27. Snapshot from the French hub (<http://www.unaf.fr/spip.php?rubrique3>) with the information we extracted

French Hub 6 (<http://www.reseau-amap.org/>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any list of organizations. However after clicking on "annuaire des AMAP" a map with various region of France was appeared. After clicking on a specific region we could find the organizations that existed in that region. Figure 28 shows a

screenshot of the organizations of a specific region with the information we extracted for those. Of course we did the same approach for all the different regions. We found 533 organizations containing information about: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (containing address, postal code and telephone numbers) and (d) the date creation.

Figure 28. Snapshot from the French hub (<http://www.reseau-amap.org/>) with the information we extracted

French Hub 7 (<http://www.acrimed.org/>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any list of organizations. After a recommendation of the French team of LiveWHAT project we could find the lists in the following URLs:

- <http://www.acrimed.org/rubrique340.html>
- <http://www.acrimed.org/rubrique305.html>

Figure 29 shows an indicative screenshot of the lists and an example of the information we extracted for one organization (the one in the red rectangle). In total, we found 41 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL and (c) a short description of the organization.

The screenshot shows the homepage of 'OBSERVATOIRE DES MÉDIAS ACRIMED'. The main navigation bar includes 'INFORMER SUR' and 'L'INFORMATION - LES MEDIAS - LES JOURNALISMES'. A search bar is present at the top left. The main content area is titled 'SITES ET BLOG D'INFORMATIONS ET D'ANALYSES'. A sidebar on the left contains 'NOTRE ASSOCIATION', 'LISTES D'INFO', 'CONTACT', 'ADHÉSION / COTISATION', and 'DON / SOUTIEN'. A sidebar on the right lists 'DES RESSOURCES' such as 'Des sites', 'Des traductions', 'Des textes', and 'Des films'. The main content area lists several resources, each with a title, a short description, and a link to the site. The following table summarizes the extracted information from the screenshot:

Perline	Title + website URL	Description
Appels d'air	"Blog culturel et autres avenants"	
Perline	ingéniere en physique des matériaux, diplômée de l'école nationale des Mines de Paris, Docteur ès-sciences-technologie-société, analyste-programmeuse et Maître en Droit public (administration du politique). Après ses études, il y a plus d'un quart de siècle, se rendant compte que son seul débouché professionnel possible était l'armée ou le nucléaire, elle a préféré passer le reste de sa vie la conscience tranquille et abandonner la recherche à but destructif."	
Fils en stock. Le portail ouvert jour et nuit	Portail perso - Sur le site : mise en ligne de dépêches d'agences, d'articles de presse, de radio ou de télévision en ligne ; accès à la presse nationale française, à quelques sites d'information alternative, dont Acrimed. [Dernière visite : 20 octobre 2004]	
Suivinfo	"Ce site a pour principal but de regrouper et de mettre à disposition des visiteurs les informations/articles/etc. provenant de différents sites via les syndications (fil rss)."	
Les Cahiers du football	"Magazine de foot et d'eau fraîche" Acrimed parmi les liens	
Lafeuille	Actualité de l'édition et de l'édition électronique. Blog.	
Vive le feu	Le blog AJT de Sébastien Fontenelle	
Décrypt Politique	"Ce site a pour but, entre autres, de donner des informations sur les partis politiques et, surtout, sur les groupuscules de France." Acrimed parmi les liens.	
Nouvelles de Turquie	Agence non gouvernementale d'information sur la Turquie. Acrimed parmi les liens.	
GuidAltern	"Outil interactif de pratiques et de ressources alternatives, dédié entre autres aux médias alternatifs, aux médiactives et à l'information"	

Figure 29. Snapshot from the French hub (<http://www.acrimed.org/>) with the information we extracted

French Hub 8 (<http://www.institut-economie-circulaire.fr/>)

The home page of the hub did not contain any list of organizations. However after clicking on "Les Membres" we found 9 categories. Each one of them contained a few organizations. Figure 30 shows an indicative screenshot the organization that fall under the category "Actualités des membres". In total we extracted 127 organizations containing information about: (a) the title, (b) the website URL and (c) contact information (including address code, the postal code and telephone numbers), (d) e-mail address, (e) a short description and (f) the date.

Figure 30. Snapshot from the French hub (<http://www.institut-economie-circulaire.fr/>)

French Hub 9 (<http://www.artisansdumonde.org/boutiques-commerce-equitable.html>)

The hub contains a list of organizations. Each organization has a link that refers to an internal web page that contains more specific information about the organization. Figure 31 shows an indicative screenshot of the internal web page of an organization with the information we extracted (in red rectangles). In total we found 151 organizations that contain the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (containing address, postal code, province, and telephone number) and (d) e-mail address.

Figure 31. Snapshot from the French hub (<http://www.artisansdumonde.org/boutiques-commerce-equitable.html>) with the information we extracted

French Hub 10 (<http://cnlii.org/>)

The homepage of the hub does not contain any list of organizations. However after clicking on “QUI SOMMES-NOUS?” and then on “Les membres de la coordination” we found a few organizations (11). For them we could extract only their title, their website URL and a short description. The following figure (Figure 32) shows an indicative screenshot of this small list.

Figure 32. Snapshot from the French hub (<http://cnlii.org/>)

French Hub 11 (<http://heterotopies.overblog.com/cartographie>)

The homepage of the hub contained a list of organizations categorized according to their locations. Figure 33 shows an indicative screenshot of the list. In total we found 318 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (only the province/city), and (d) a short description of the organization.

Figure 33. Snapshot from the French hub (<http://heterotopies.overblog.com/cartographie>)

5.5 Spanish Networks

Spanish Hub 1 (<http://15mpedia.org/wiki/>)

This hub contains information about several categories of individual sites. We managed to extract information about the organizations from eight categories. These categories are shown in Figure 34.

Figure 34. Snapshot from the Spanish hub (<http://15mpedia.org/wiki/>)

After clicking on each category a list of organizations revealed. However each category contained different information about the organizations. This means that we had to work with each category as if it is a different hub. In total we found 876 organizations, containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (mostly the area), (d) the province/city they are located in (or they are active at) and (e) e-mail address.

Spanish Hub 2 (<http://www.economiasolidaria.org/entidades>)

This hub contains a list of organizations with specific information about them. The results are splitted in many pages. More specifically, the organizations are shown in the form of a table where each row represents an organization and the columns are the different characteristics/information of an organization. An indicative screenshot is shown in Figure 35.

Entidad	Localidad y Código Postal	Provincia	Actividad	Web
PROEMPLEO	MADRID - 28013	MADRID	Otras actividades de servicios Inserción Socio-Laboral Asesoría empresas	www.proempleo.org
LA CEIBA	Madrid - 28014	MADRID	Tienda de la solidaridad Comercio Justo	www.laceiba.org
Abierto Hasta el Amanecer	Madrid - 28018	MADRID	Programas de Participación y desarrollo territorial. Servicios de gestión, animación, educación y asesoramiento. Formación presencial, on-line y mixta (TIC, S, intervención, empleo, autoempleo, participación, empoderamiento, género...) Proyectos de Inserción Socio laboral con mujeres Inserción socio-laboral de colectivos en riesgo de exclusión social	www.abiertomadrid.coop
ANDROMINES	MONTCADA I REIXAC - 08110	BARCELONA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recuperación Inserción Socio-Laboral Tienda de la solidaridad Otras actividades de servicios 	www.andromines.org

Figure 35. Snapshot from the Spanish hub (<http://www.economiasolidaria.org/entidades>)

Furthermore each organization contains a link, which refers to an internal web page that contains more information for the organization. Figure 36 shows an indicative screenshot of the web page of such an organization.

Figure 36. Snapshot from the Spanish hub (<http://www.economiasolidaria.org/entidades>) with the information we extracted

In total we found 406 organizations that contained the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (containing address, postal code and telephone and fax numbers), (d) e-mail address, (e) a short description and (f) creation date.

Spanish Hub 3 (<http://www.mecambio.net/>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any list of organizations. After a recommendation of the Spanish team of LiveWHAT project, we searched for lists in the following URLs:

- <http://www.mecambio.net/blog/category/cambio-basico/finanzas-seguros/>
- <http://www.mecambio.net/blog/category/cambio-integral/>

Figure 37 shows a screenshot of the list of organizations that can be found after following the first link above. In total we identified 67 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL and (c) a short description.

MECAMBIO
ALTERNATIVAS PARA UN CONSUMO RESPONSABLE

MECAMBIO QUIENES SOMOS CAMBIO BÁSICO CAMBIO INTEGRAL PREGUNTS

FINANZAS Y SEGUROS

Si existe hoy un agente global responsable y beneficiario directo de la crisis es, sin duda, la Banca y el sistema financiero. Su funcionamiento (y enormes beneficios) se ha basado en la especulación financiera global, en la economía virtual y en el negocio de la usura con la que han hipotecado nuestros futuros. Sin embargo **nos presentan a la banca convencional como un mal inevitable**, una infraestructura de servicio básico que hay que rescatar a todo riesgo. Quizás vaya siendo hora de **desmontar estas mentiras y cambiarnos a cooperativas de ahorro y otras formas de gestionar nuestro dinero, de asegurar nuestros bienes, de financiar nuestros proyectos y de realizar transacciones y compras**. Si quieres conocer más iniciativas de las que presentamos aquí, te recomendamos este artículo de Ouishare.

Banca ética	Banca ética	Banca ética
FIARE BANCA ETICA	COOP57 SERVICIOS FINANCIEROS ÉTICOS Y SOLIDARIOS	TRIODOS BANK
FIARE tiene como objetivo declarado ser un banco en manos de la ciudadanía. Actúa desde el 2005 como agencia y después área en España de Banca Popolare Etica (un banco ético con larga trayectoria en Italia).	Coop57 da la posibilidad de abrir una libreta de ahorro, o de beneficiarse de préstamos. Los ahorros invertidos en Coop57 sirven exclusivamente a financiar proyectos de la economía social.	Triodos es un banco europeo (de origen Holandés) con 35 años de experiencia en banca ética y sostenible, comparado con Fiare o Coop57 es un modelo más basado en la banca tradicional, construido sin una base social. Inició su actividad en España en el 2004.
F Para guardar tus ahorros y/o abrir una cuenta corriente. www.fiarebancaetica.coop	F Para guardar tus ahorros coop57.coop	F Para abrir una cuenta corriente en cualquier punto del Estado triodos.es

Figure 37. Snapshot from the Spanish hub (<http://www.mecambio.net/>)

Spanish Hub 4 (<http://www.bdonline.org/>)

The homepage of the hub contains an interactive map with organizations. However, the information from this map could not be parsed and we managed to retrieve all the organizations from a relevant webpage <http://mapa.vivirsinempleo.org/map/> (it is actually the source webpage for the interactive map that is exploited in the hub). Figure 38 shows the list of organizations in the red rectangle and Figure 39 shows the information we extracted for each organization. We found 307 organizations with the following information: (a) title , (b) website URL, (c) contact information and (d) e-mail address.

Figure 38. Snapshot from the Spanish hub (<http://www.bdtonline.org/>)

Figure 39. Snapshot from the Spanish hub (<http://www.bdtonline.org/>) with the information we have extracted

Spanish Hub 5 (<http://www.redautogestion.com/directorio-autogestion/>)

The homepage of the hub contains a list of sites containing several information. Each item in the list refers to an organization and it is a link to an internal webpage that contains detailed information about the organization. Figure 40 shows an indicative screenshot of the detailed information of a specific organization. In total we identified 24 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, (d) short description and (e) date.

DIRECTORIO DE AUTOGESTIÓN

Este es un directorio de proyectos que se rijan por principios autogestionarios y horizontales, donde la explotación no tenga cabida y todas las personas estén en un plano de igualdad.

VEER – CERVEZA ARTESANA ECOLÓGICA *Title*

— Regresar al Directorio

Categoría: *Producción Ecológica*

Sitio web: www.cervezaveer.com *Website URL*

Cerveza Veer nace en 2009 con la idea principal de tener que dejar de buscar trabajo y trabajar para un jefe. Queríamos hacer un proyecto gestionado por nosotras mismas para poder ser algo más autosuficientes económicamente, pero teníamos claro que no queríamos que fuese un proyecto meramente económico, sino también que tuviese un contenido político, algo que cuando estuviésemos en una feria vendiendo nuestra cerveza o en un bar, la gente se preguntara cosas y viera otra forma de funcionar. *Description*

1362 Visitas

Teléfono: 655.47.90.30
Teléfono: 620.007.678 *Contact Info*
Ciudad: Sebúlcór
Provincia: Segovia
RCA: Si

Search the site

PÁGINAS

- Buscamos espacios vacíos en cesión de uso
- Autogestión en Madrid

ENTRADAS RECIENTES

- Celebración del Año Nuevo Bangla
- (NOT-AFTER-BUT)_POSTWORK PARTY
- VIERNES 27_CENADOR EN V34
- 310 EMPRESAS OKUPADAS, SUMA Y SIGUE.
- Teatro de los sentidos: El Quijote

Figure 40. Snapshot from the Spanish hub (<http://www.redautogestion.com/directorio-autogestion/>) with the information we extracted

Spanish Hub 6 (<http://www.todoporlapraxis.es/?cat=1>)

The homepage of the hub contains the list organizations in the form of posts in a blog site. Each post refers to an organization (or an individual activity). The following figure (Figure 41) shows an indicative snapshot of the organizations/activities that can be found in the hub. In total we found 58 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) description and (d) the date.

Bookcrossing San Fermín *Title*

9-Marzo-2015 | Sección: *Procesos* *Date*

Durante muchos años vecinos de San Fermín llevan autogestionando una biblioteca comunitaria ya que en su barrio carecen de este equipamiento. En el año 2008 el ayuntamiento de Madrid anuncio la construcción de esta Biblioteca y sin embargo los vecinos de San Fermín siguen esperando. Esta intervención forma parte de unas de las acciones vecinales para reclamar y demandar este equipamiento denunciando el incumplimiento de este compromiso. *Description*

Figure 41. Snapshot from the Spanish hub (<http://www.todoporlapraxis.es/?cat=1>) with the information we extracted

Spanish Hub 7 (http://ludus.org.es/es/projects?province_id=31)

The hub contains a list of organization in its home page. For each organization some informative details are given. Furthermore each organization has a link that points to an internal webpage and contains more specific information for the selected organization. Figure 42 shows a screenshot of such a web page; in red rectangles we show the information we extracted for each organization. In total we have found 83 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, (d) a short description and (e) e-mail address.

Figure 42. Snapshot from the Spanish hub (http://ludus.org.es/es/projects?province_id=31) with the information we extracted

Spanish Hub 8 (<http://www.nodo50.org/puzlea/ocupacion.htm>)

The homepage of the hub contains several organizations/activities. The only information that exists for those is: (a) title information and (b) their website URL (for some organization there is no information about the website URL; in those cases we have extracted their e-mail address). The total number of organizations we found is 69.

Figure 43. Snapshot from the Spanish hub (<http://www.nodo50.org/puzlea/ocupacion.htm>) with the information we extracted

Spanish Hub 9 (<http://auditoriaciudadana.net/>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any list of organizations. However there is an interactive map with the label “Nodos locales”. Each point in the map is an organization. From this map we extracted 23 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL and (c) e-mail address.

Figure 44. Snapshot from the Spanish hub (<http://auditoriaciudadana.net/>) with the information we extracted

Spanish Hub 10 (<http://www.hispacoop.es/home>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any list of organizations. However after clicking on “Organización Cooperativa” and then on “Cooperativas y Grupos de Consumo Ecológico” a list of organizations revealed. The organizations are splitted into several pages. Figure 45 shows an indicative screenshot of the list. In total we found 170 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL and (c) contact information (containing address, postal code and telephone numbers), (d) the city/area they are located in, (e) e-mail address and (f) the date they have been created.

pero no solo eso. Además de conseguir una alimentación sana, libre de residuos, transgénicos, pesticidas etc, este movimiento ayuda a revitalizar el campo y la economía local así como a fomentar el consumo responsable.

Se trata, en suma, de apostar por una **economía sostenible** que haga un uso más eficaz de los recursos, más verde y competitiva.

En estas experiencias son los propios consumidores los que impulsan cambios en el concepto de consumo, orientándolo hacia uno que cuestione su origen y naturaleza pero que, sobre todo, reduzca su impacto social y medioambiental.

Algunas de estas agrupaciones han crecido lo suficiente y se han constituido en cooperativas **con una filosofía y unos valores propios**.

El paulatino crecimiento y la posterior organización representativa de este movimiento lo sitúan ya como un actor relevante en los ámbitos de la economía social, consumerista y agroecológica.

Hispacoop ha elaborado esta **base de datos** de cooperativas, asociaciones y grupos de consumo ecológico con el fin de ayudar a **identificar y cuantificar estas experiencias y así** darles una mayor visibilidad.

Si quieres que tu grupo de consumo, asociación o cooperativa figure en nuestra base de datos, envíanos un **mensaje** con tu teléfono y nos pondremos en contacto contigo.

Cooperativas, asociaciones y grupos de consumo de productos ecológicos (170/-)

A Cova da Terra DIRECCIÓN: das Noreas, 2 27001 Lugo TELÉFONO: 982.23.02.11 Web	A Gradicela DIRECCIÓN: Bautista Andrade, 64 Pontevedra Web
A Xoaniña DIRECCIÓN: Venezuela, 78 15404 Ferrol A Coruña TELÉFONO: 981.93.08.68 PERSONA DE CONTACTO: Mercedes Web	Acocon DIRECCIÓN: Concha Espina, 7 Muriedas Cantabria Web
Aigua Clara AÑO DE CONSTITUCIÓN: 2003 DIRECCIÓN: Mercado Municipal de Ontinyent TELÉFONO: 96 244 24 93 Web	Ajo Loko DIRECCIÓN: Calatrava, 19 Madrid
Almocafre AÑO DE CONSTITUCIÓN: 2000 DIRECCIÓN: Avda. de los Custodios, 5 14004 Córdoba Córdoba TELÉFONO: 957.41.40.50-957.24.94.79 PERSONA DE CONTACTO: Carmen Casas Web	Amor a la Tierra Madrid Web

Figure 45. Snapshot from the Spanish hub (<http://www.hispacoop.es/home>) with the information we extracted

5.6 Polish Networks

Polish Hub 1 (<http://www.ekonomiaspoleczna.pl/>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain a list with organizations. However after clicking on “Praktyków ES” and then on “Bazę ośrodków wsparcia ekonomii społecznej” a list of organizations revealed. Each organization in the list has a link that refers to an internal webpage containing more information about the organization. Figure 46 shows an indicative screenshot of a specific webpage of an organization of the Polish hub. In total we found 39 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact

information (containing address, postal code, area, and telephone address), (d) e-mail address and (e) the period of activity.

The screenshot shows a webpage titled "MAPA OŚRODKÓW WSPARCIA ES" with a navigation menu in the top right corner. The main content is divided into two sections: "DANE KONTAKTOWE" (Contact Info) and "START" (Project Details).

Contact Info:

- Adres: ul. Poznańska 42, 88-100 Inowrocław
- tel: 52 357 06 02
- e-mail: kpces@bvd.pl
- www: <http://www.kpces.bvd.pl>

Project Details (START):

Title: Kujawsko-Paluckie Centrum Ekonomii Społecznej

Period of activity: 10.2013 - 09.2015

województwo: kujawsko-pomorskie

rodzaj wsparcia:

- usługi prawne, księgowo, marketingowe, doradztwo finansowe
- doradztwo (indywidualne i grupowe) oraz szkolenia umożliwiające uzyskanie wiedzy i umiejętności potrzebnych do założenia i prowadzenia działalności w sektorze ekonomii społecznej
- rozwój partnerstwa lokalnego na rzecz rozwoju ekonomii społecznej
- promocję ekonomii społecznej i zatrudnienia w sektorze ekonomii społecznej
- wsparcie dla osób fizycznych zamierzających rozpocząć działalność gospodarczą w formie spółdzielni społecznej
- wsparcie dla osób prawnych chcących powołać spółdzielnię społeczną
- działania prowadzące do poszukiwania i testowania długookresowych źródeł finansowania instytucji odczyna sektora ekonomii społecznej oraz spółdzielni społecznych
- inne

forma prawna lidera projektu: uczelnia

grupy docelowe: Osoby fizyczne, w tym bezrobotne, długotrwale bezrobotne, nieaktywne zawodowe (w tym uczące się) oraz zatrudnione w mikro, małych i średnich przedsiębiorstwach z powiatu inowrocławskiego, znińskiego i mogileńskiego.

finansowanie: Program Operacyjny Kapitał Ludzki

inne projekty tego samego lidera: [Rozwój i funkcjonowanie Kujawsko-Paluckiego Centrum Ekonomii Społecznej \(01.2011 - 12.2013\)](#), [Kujawsko-Paluckie Centrum Ekonomii Społecznej powiat inowrocławski, zniński i mogileński \(10.2013 - 09.2015\)](#)

informacje dodatkowe o projekcie: Projekt skierowany do osób zagrożonych wykluczeniem społecznym.

Figure 46. Snapshot from the Polish hub (<http://www.ekonomiaspoleczna.pl>) with the information we extracted

Polish Hub 2

[http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&szukanie=zaawans1&kryt typ in styt multi=74&baza=13](http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&szukanie=zaawans1&kryt%20typ%20in%20styt%20multi=74&baza=13))

The website contained a list of 149 organizations in 5 pages of results. Each page contained 20 results and as a result we could not retrieve all the organizations (it seems that there was a limit to show only the first 100 results if there are more than this). So we selected all the available option from the menu "województwo". This splitted the 149 organizations among the selected options and number of results were lower for each selection. In total there were 16 different choices for the "województwo" selection and finally we could retrieve all the organizations. Figure 47 shows the list of organizations.

ngo.pl **bazy.ngo.pl** wyszukiwarka | lista baz | jak szukać

Co to są organizacje pozarządowe?

Centra wolontariatu

CO? nazwa [?] GDZIE? miejscowość [?] województwo [?]

Organizacje pozarządowe – dane statystyczne

Lista baz

Jak szukać

Jak dodać i aktualizować

Korzyści z obecności w bazie

Kontakt

Liczba wyników: 149 - wyszukiwanie zwraca powyżej 100 wyników, doprecyzuj z

Sortowanie: nazwa (A-Z) (Z-A) miejscowość (A-Z) (Z-A)

Stowarzyszenie Regionalne Centrum Wolontariatu w Krakowie
Regional Volunteer Center in Cracow
Kraków, woj. małopolskie
Numer KRS: 0000528791

[więcej](#)

Wsparcia organizacjom pozarządowym udzielają również:

Drzewickie Centrum Wolontariatu "Ofiarna dłoń"
Volunteer Center in Drzewica
Drzewica, woj. łódzkie
Numer KRS: 0000377275

pp

Figure 47. Snapshot from the Polish hub (http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&szukanie=zaawans1&kryt_typ_instyt_multi=74&baza=13)

For each result there is an internal link (“więcej”) and after clicking it a particular web page containing more information for the organization opens. In total we found 147 distinct organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) e-mail, (d) contact information and (e) date/year. This information is shown in a red rectangle in the following figure (Figure 48).

ngo.pl **bazy.ngo.pl** wyszukiwarka | lista baz | jak szukać

[powrót do wyników wyszukiwania](#)

Stowarzyszenie Regionalne Centrum Wolontariatu w Krakowie *title*

Regional volunteer Center in Cracow
forma prawna: stowarzyszenie

[wejdźcie dla organizacji](#)

Adres siedziby, kontakt

Stowarzyszenie Regionalne Centrum Wolontariatu w Krakowie
Mogilska 102 lok. 1
31-546 Kraków
Polska

contact info

gmina: Kraków
powiat: Kraków
województwo: małopolskie

Adres do korespondencji:

Stowarzyszenie Regionalne Centrum Wolontariatu w Krakowie
Krasickiego 18, II piętro, 30-503 Kraków

contact info

Tel: 883 427 830
Faks:

E-mail: krakow@wolontariat.org.pl
Strona: www.wolontariat.org.pl/krakow *website/e-mail*

Sposób, godziny kontaktu: poniedziałek, wtorek, czwartek w godz. 9.00 - 15.00;
środa w godz. 11.00 - 19.00

Siedziba niedostępna dla osób niepełnosprawnych. Biuro znajduje się na II piętrze w kamienicy, w której nie ma windy.

Rok powstania: 2014 *date/year*

O nas

Regionalne Centrum Wolontariatu w Krakowie powstało w 2010 roku przy Fundacji Biuro Inicjatyw Społecznych, która umożliwiła i wspierała jego działania poprzez realizację wielu projektów mających na celu promocję i rozwój wolontariatu w Małopolsce.
Od 2014 roku Centrum działa jako samodzielne stowarzyszenie.

Map

Figure 48. Snapshot from the Polish hub (http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&szukanie=zaawans1&kryt_typ_instyt_multi=74&baza=13) with the information we extracted

We should note here that the following hubs (that were also requested from the LiveWHAT Polish team) have a similar format with the previous hub. Therefore the process for extracting information for the organizations they contain is similar. During the analysis of these hubs we faced the same problem with the limitation of the results that could be shown to the users. In these cases we retrieved the results by specifying the provinces of the organizations (using all the available choices from the drop down list). This technique allowed us to retrieve the maximum number of results (however not all of them). Here we are listing the URLs of these hubs with the total number of organizations we found for each one of them.

- http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&szukanie=zaawans1&kryt_typ_instyt_multi=83&baza=64 (53 organizations)
- http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&szukanie=zaawans1&kryt_typ_instyt_multi=114&baza=105 (97 organizations)
- http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&szukanie=zaawans1&kryt_typ_instyt_multi=89&baza=78 (1149 organizations)
- http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&kryt_nazwa=&kryt_miasto=&kryt_woj=&kryt_pola=12&kryt_typ_instyt_multi=17&baza=1&szukanie=zaawans1 (1600 organizations)
- http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&kryt_nazwa=&kryt_miasto=&kryt_kraj=&kryt_ekk=8&szukanie=ekk (561 organizations)
- http://bazy.ngo.pl/search/wyniki.asp?wyniki=1&kryt_nazwa=&kryt_miasto=&kryt_woj=&kryt_pola=24&kryt_typ_instyt_multi=17&baza=1&szukanie=zaawans1 (1600 organizations)

Polish Hub 6 (<http://inkubatory.pl/mapa-inkubatorow/>)

The website for the hub contains a few organizations, categorized based on their location. After selecting a particular location we could extract information about the organization (or organizations) that are located there. In total we found 49 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) contact information (containing address and telephone number) and (d) a short description. Figure 49 shows an indicative screenshot of the hub.

inkubatory.pl AIP WYDARZENIA MAPA INKUBATORÓW OFERTA AIP BLOG SEED CAPITAL DOŁĄCZ DO AIP

Find the best location!
Enjoy a perfect office for your startup!

AIP stanowi obecnie sieć 50 inkubatorów, funkcjonujących w 24 polskich miastach. W ramach Programu AIP otrzymujesz dostęp do biur inkubatorów za pomocą karty magnetycznej AIP, możliwość korzystania z multimedialnych sal konferencyjnych i sal spotkań, zapewniamy Ci nieograniczony dostęp do strefy coworkingu, połączenie wi-fi oraz możliwość korzystania z komputerów, drukarek oraz profesjonalnego oprogramowania AIP.

Znajdź najlepszą dla siebie lokalizację

- [AIP Białystok](#)
- [AIP Bielsko-Biała](#)
- [AIP Bydgoszcz](#)
- [AIP Bytom](#)
- [AIP Częstochowa](#)
- [AIP Gdańsk](#)
- [AIP Katowice](#)
- [AIP Kielce](#)
- [AIP Kraków](#)
- [AIP Lublin](#)
- [AIP Łódź](#)
- [AIP Olsztyn](#)
- [AIP Opole](#)
- [AIP Płock](#)
- [AIP Poznań](#)
- [AIP Radom](#)
- [AIP Rzeszów](#)
- [AIP Siedlce](#)
- [AIP Szczecin](#)
- [AIP Toruń](#)
- [AIP Warszawa](#)
- [AIP Wrocław](#)
- [AIP Zabrze](#)

Figure 49. Snapshot from the Polish hub (<http://inkubatory.pl/mapa-inkubatorow/>) with the information we extracted

Polish Hub 7 (<http://www.ffl.org.pl/pl/czlonkowie>)

This hub contained only a few organizations (12 in number), therefore we extracted them manually. For every organization in the list there is a link with title “więcej” that refers to a webpage containing more information about the organization (see Figure 50). As already mentioned we found 12 organizations, containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, (d) e-mail address, (e) date and (f) a short description.

Figure 50. Snapshot from the Polish hub (<http://www.ffl.org.pl/pl/czlonkowie>) showing the list of organizations.

Polish Hub 8 (<https://kolektywnie.wordpress.com/category/kooperatywy-spozywcze/>)

The webpage of the hub contains a list of organizations, organized based on their location. In total we found 27 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL and (c) contact information (city).

Polish Individual Websites

The list of individual websites has been analyzed manually. This means that we extracted manually information about the corresponding organizations after visiting them in a web browser. The analysis of the individual websites revealed 25 organizations and we extracted the following information: (a) the title, (b) the website URL, (c) contact information, (d) e-mail address and (e) the dates that the organization has been active.

The only problem we faced with the individual websites is that we could not analyze the following websites because they no longer exist or they seem to be irrelevant.

- <http://kwiatkibratki.pl/>
- <http://www.forumkwiatowe.pl/>

5.7 Swiss Networks

Swiss Hub 1 (<http://www.observatoire-esspace.eu/>)

This webpage contains a list of organizations containing various description and information about them. Figure 51 shows a screenshot of the hub; one indicative organization is shown

in the red rectangle. The total number of organizations we found for the hub is 674, with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (including address, postal code, and telephone number), and (d) e-mail address.

677 Structures

Organization Name	Address	Contact Info	Website
...Et Faits Planète	59 rue du Pont 74130 Bonneville France	09 62 60 90 74 contact@etfaitsplanete.org	http://www.etfaitsplanete.org
42(prod)	Rue Rotshchild 50 1202 Genève Suisse	022 735 31 55 info@42prod.com	http://www.42prod.com
A la croisée des âges	CP 222 1213 Petit-lancy Suisse	077 413 40 67 paulasbs6@yahoo.fr	
A PARTÉ	Bd. Saint Georges 15/ rue des Jardins 12 217 1211 Genève 8 Suisse	a-parté@bluewin.ch	http://a-parté.ch/
AACE société coopérative - atelier d'architecture coopératif & engineering	Rue Hugo de Senger, 3 1205 Genève Suisse	078 642 56 17 info@aace.ch	http://www.aace.ch
Aatea	Le Chanois 25380 VAUCLUSOTTE France	03 81 67 53 95 aatea@gmail.com	

Figure 51. Snapshot from the Swiss hub (<http://www.observatoire-esspace.eu/>) showing the list of organizations.

Swiss Hub 2 (<http://www.sel-suisse.ch/>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any lists of organizations. However after clicking on the menu item (found on the upper menu bar) “Trouver un SEL” a new menu bar with various locations of Switzerland revealed (shown in Figure 52). After clicking on them, the organizations that are located in this area are shown. Figure 53 shows the organizations that are located in Geneva. In total we found 17 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information and (d) e-mail address.

Accueil **Trouver un SEL**

SEL-SUISSE.CH

Bienvenue sur le portail des SELs suisses

Fribourg

Figure 52. Snapshot from the Swiss hub (<http://www.sel-suisse.ch/>)

Figure 53. Snapshot from the Swiss hub (<http://www.sel-suisse.ch/>) showing the list of organizations.

Swiss Hub 3 (<http://www.acpch.ch/liens/>)

The homepage of the hub contains some links having as titles different locations of Switzerland. Once clicked these locations reveal lists of organizations that are active into the corresponding location. Each organization has a link that refers to a web page containing more information about the organization. Figure 54 shows an indicative screenshot of an organization with the information we extracted. In total we found 30 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information (containing address and telephone number) and (d) e-mail address.

Figure 54. Snapshot from the Swiss hub (<http://www.acpch.ch/liens/>) with the information we extracted

Swiss Hub 4 (<http://www.decroissance-bern.ch/index.php>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any list of organizations. However after clicking on “Links” (shown on the menu on the upper left), a list of organizations revealed. We found 22 organizations and for them we could find only: (a) their title, (b) their website URL and (c) a short description for some of them.

Figure 55. Snapshot from the Swiss hub (<http://www.decroissance-bern.ch/index.php>) with the information we extracted

Swiss Hub 5 (<https://radar.squat.net/en>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any list of organizations; it contained a list of related events. However after clicking on “Groups” (from the menu on the upper right) and selecting only “Switzerland” from the list of available countries, a list of organizations that are located in Switzerland revealed. Each organization has a link that points to an internal web page showing more information for the organization. Figure 57 shows an indicative screenshot of such an organization. We found 40 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, and (d) e-mail address.

radar.squat.net ^{NEW}

1. select "Groups"

Events **Groups** How to... Login

English

Groups

3. List of organizations

Aargau
Bahnhofstrasse, Aarau Je nach Ort und Anlass
action/protest/camp, bar/cafe, discussion/presentation, food, music

AJZ Biel
Kongresshausparkplatz, Biel-Bienne
bar/cafe, music, party

AKW Biel
Johann-Renfer-Strasse 3, Biel/Bienne
bar/cafe, book shop/info shop/library, course/workshop, discussion/presentation, exhibition, film, food, free shop, meeting, music, party, theater, work space/diy

Blaushuus at Koch
Rautistrasse 22/ Fhüelastrasse 54, Zürich from now till revolution
action/protest/camp, course/workshop, discussion/presentation, exhibition, film, food, free shop, music, party

Country
 Switzerland

City
 Zürich (14)
 Basel (5)
 Biel-Bienne (3)
 Biel/Bienne (3)
 Lausanne (3)
 Winterthur (3)
 Bern (2)
 Aarau (1)
 Baden (1)
 Bremgarten (1)
 Geneva (1)
 Rochefort (1)
 St. Gallen (1)
 Wetzikon ZH (1)
 Zug (1)

Status
 squat (15)

2. select "Country"

Figure 56. Snapshot from the Swiss hub (<https://radar.squat.net/en>)

Aargrau

View Events Archive

Aargrau Title

Demonstrationen, Strassenpartys, Besetzungen, Konzerte und Anderes in Aarau...

opening times:
Je nach Ort und Anlass

categories: action/protest/camp, bar/cafe, discussion/presentation, food, music

online: <http://www.aargrau.ch> Website URL

email: info@aargrau.ch e-mail

location:
Bahnhofplatz
Bahnhofstrasse
5000 Aarau
Switzerland

Sportanlage Schachen
Schwimmbadstrasse
7
5000 Aarau
Switzerland

Description

Figure 57. Snapshot from the Swiss hub (<https://radar.squat.net/en>) with the information we extracted

Swiss Hub 6 (<http://www.wbg-schweiz.ch/mitglieder.html>)

The website of the hub contains a list of organizations sorted in alphabetical order (Project Syndicate). Figure 58 shows the list of organizations that start from 'A'. In total we found 534 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information and (d) e-mail address.

Home
Aktuell
Veranstaltungen
Dienstleistungen
Finanzierung
Zeitschrift Wohnen
Wohnbaugenossenschaften Schweiz
Regionalverbände
Mitglieder
► **Genossenschaften**
Fördermitglieder
Assoziierte Mitglieder
Adressmutationen
Links
Wohnungssuche
Wohnbaugenossenschaften Schweiz im Facebook
Empfehlen

Genossenschaften

Die im Internet aufgeführten Genossenschaften entsprechen nicht dem vollständigen Mitgliederverzeichnis von Wohnbaugenossenschaften Schweiz. Die Nennung im Internet erfolgt nur und mit ausdrücklicher Zustimmung unserer Mitglieder. Änderungswünsche und Neueintragen müssen dem Verband [mitgeteilt](#) werden.

Genossenschaft suchen:

► A | B | C | D | E | F | G | H | I | J | K | L | M | N | O | P | Q | R | S | T | U | V | W | X | Y | Z

Suchbegriff:

ABK Allgemeine Baugenossenschaft Kriens 6011 Kriens info@abk-kriens.ch www.abk-kriens.ch	
Allgem. Wohn- und Baugenossenschaft (AWB) 4054 Basel thomas_bitterli@hispeed.ch	
Allgemeine Bau- und Wohngenosenschaft Biel 2503 Biel info@abw-biel.ch	
Allgemeine Baugenossenschaft Luzern (ABL) 6000 Luzern info@abl.ch www.abl.ch	
Allgemeine Baugenossenschaft Winterthur 8407 Winterthur christian_gehardt@gmx.ch www.qwg-winterthur.ch	
Allgemeine Baugenossenschaft Zürich ABZ 8055 Zürich info@abz.ch www.abz.ch	

Figure 58. Snapshot from the Swiss hub (<http://www.wbg-schweiz.ch/mitglieder.html>) with list of organization starting from 'A'

Swiss Hub 7 (<http://www.apres-ge.ch/>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any lists of organizations. However after selecting “ECONOMIE SOCIALE ET SOLIDAIRE” (found on the upper menu bar) and then on “SITES INTERNET” a list of organizations revealed. The list is organized in several pages. Figure 59 shows an indicative screenshot; the red rectangles denote the information we extracted for each organization. We found 149 organizations with information about: (a) their title, (b) their website URL, and (c) a short description.

ECONOMIE SOCIALE ET SOLIDAIRE LA CHAMBRE PRESTATIONS

Sites internet

SHARE

Liens internet

Pays: <Any> Thématiques: <Any>

Mots-clés:

Lancer la recherche →

APRES-VD *Title*
<http://www.zen3.net/apres-vd> *website URL*
 Le site de la Chambre de l'économie sociale et solidaire vaudoise *Description*
 Pays: Suisse
 Thématiques: ESS

Guide des Achats Professionnels Responsables
<http://www.achats-responsables.ch/>
 Le Guide des Achats professionnels Responsables présente non seulement de très nombreuses recommandations pour divers domaines d'achats (matériel de bureau, mobilier, vêtements professionnels, restauration, entretien des bâtiments).
 Pays: Suisse
 Thématiques: Commerce équitable

Diplôme de formation continue en Management durable - Université de Genève
<http://sustainablemanagement.ch/modules/das.html>
 Le diplôme de formation continue en Management durable est destiné aux cadres, professionnels et managers appelés à mettre en oeuvre une stratégie de bonne gouvernance intégrant les principes du développement durable.
 Pays: Suisse
 Thématiques: Gestion/management

Figure 59. Snapshot from the Swiss hub (<http://www.apres-ge.ch/>) with the information we extracted

Swiss Hub 8 (<http://www.lets.ch/links.php>)

Figure 60 shows the homepage of the hub; the area inside the red rectangle contains the list of organizations. We found 29 organizations in the hub with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL and (c) contact information.

LETS Tauschnetz Zürich

Interessante Links

LETS.ch

Home
Agenda
Spielregeln
Mitglied werden
Downloads
Links
Kontakt
Forum
Cyclos

LETS-Flyer (pdf)

LETS.ch

Tauschen nach Lust und Laune

Bei LETS werden kreative und praktische Arbeiten getauscht. Alle Mitglieder bringen Talente und Leistungen ein, um sie besonders gut können und ihnen Spass machen.

Tauschnetzwerke

[Schweiz] Aargau, Basel, Bern, Fribourg, Genève, Graubünden, Jura, Luzern, Obwalden, St. Gallen, Solothurn, Thurgau, Ticino, Uri, Vaud, Zürich, sonstiges...

Aargau, **TALENT**

TALENT Schweiz
Region CH-Nordwestschweiz
Postadresse: Verein Talent Schweiz, 5000 Aarau
Kontakt: Rahel Hirsiger, Tel.: 044 586 84 53
E-Mail: Kontakt über Formular aufnehmen
Internet: www.talent.ch

Basel, **BNB, BonNetzBon**

Region CH-Nordwestschweiz

Änderungen vorbehalten / Stand: 23.07.2014

Herr Frau * Benötigte Felder ** mind. eine Angabe wird benötigt

Vorname * Name *

Telefon ** Email **

hier Tauschnetzwerk wählen

Mitteilung / Anfrage an ausgewähltes Tauschnetzwerk

*Kopie an mich:
 ja

senden

Figure 60. Snapshot from the Swiss hub (<http://www.lets.ch/links.php>) with the information we extracted

Swiss Hub 9 (<http://www.loconomie.ch>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any list of organizations. However, after clicking on “Kontakt” and then on “Links” (found on the upper menu bar) a list of 3 organizations revealed. We exported the information about them manually (only title and website URL).

Start Aktuell Hintergrund Kooperationsstelle Lehrgang Unterlagen Über uns Archiv **Kontakt**

Links

[Deutscheschweizer Verband für Regionale Vertragslandwirtschaft](#)

[Westschweizer Verband FRACP](#)

[Deutsches Netzwerk für Solidarische Landwirtschaft](#)

copyleft - Kooperationsstelle für solidarische Landwirtschaft

Figure 61. Snapshot from the Swiss hub (<http://www.loconomie.ch>) with the information we extracted

Swiss Hub 10 (<http://www.ueca.ch/>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any list of organizations. However, after clicking on “MEMBRES” (found on the upper menu bar) a list of organizations was found. After clicking on each organization more information about it were shown. We found 27 organizations with the following information: (a) title and (b) website URL.

Figure 62. Snapshot from the Swiss hub (<http://www.ueca.ch/>) with the information we extracted

Swiss Individual Websites

The list of individual websites has been analyzed manually. This means that we extracted manually information about the corresponding organizations after visiting them in a web browser. The analysis of the individual websites revealed 9 organizations and we extracted the following information: (a) the title, (b) the website URL, (c) contact information, (d) e-mail address and (e) a short description.

5.8 Italian Networks

Italian Hub 1 (<http://www.economiasolidale.net/>)

This website cannot be handled as a hub since it does not contain any lists of organizations. It contains many lists of particular events in several cities/areas around Italy. Therefore we could not extract anything from this website.

Italian Hub 2 (<http://www.retegas.org/>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any list of organizations. However after clicking on "Gruppi" (found on the upper menu bar), a list of organizations revealed. Each organization has a link that refers to an internal webpage containing more information about the corresponding organization; Figure 63 shows an indicative screenshot of such an internal webpage. We found 1000 organizations in this hub containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, (d) e-mail address, (e) a short description and (f) date.

Dall'archivio dei Gruppi di Acquisto Solidale aderenti alla rete nazionale:

TALE' GAS *Title*

Riferimento: MARGHERITA GINTOLI

Indirizzo: VIA FERRO DI CAVALLO 36 *Contact Info*
97018 SCICLI (Ragusa)

Telefono: 3338262291 *website URL*

e-mail: gintoli.margherita@virgilio.it *e-mail* Fax: - *website URL*

Sito web: <http://www.tale.altervista.org/>

Mailing-list:

Presentazione:

Ultimo agg. dati: 09/01/2015 *date*

Description

- Per gli interessati ad aderire al "TALE' GAS" di Ragusa: si consiglia di contattare direttamente il G.A.S. utilizzando i vari recapiti indicati sopra; è abbastanza inutile lasciare commenti qui di seguito in quanto raramente i responsabili del G.A.S. passano per leggerli.
- Per i produttori: gli indirizzi e-mail e gli altri dati sensibili reperibili attraverso questo archivio NON sono pubblici ed i proprietari NON hanno espresso alcun consenso per essere contattati per offerte commerciali di qualsiasi natura.
- Per i responsabili del "TALE' GAS": in caso di necessità di aggiornamento di questi dati, chi ne aveva richiesto la pubblicazione, può richiedere le modifiche scrivendole come commento in questa pagina (la modifica effettiva della scheda avverrà entro qualche settimana).

I dati qui riportati sono pubblicati con il consenso degli interessati che possono in qualunque momento, ai sensi dell'art. 7 del dlgs 196/2003, richiederne la cancellazione scrivendo ai gestori del sito.

Figure 63. Snapshot from the Italian hub (<http://www.retegas.org/>) with the information we extracted

Italian Hub 3 (<http://www.retecosol.org/>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any list of organizations. However, after clicking on "Link" (found on the upper left) some categories of organizations revealed (i.e. "Commercio Equo", "Consumo Solidale", "Cooperative Sociali", etc.). Each category contained a list of organizations. We found 83 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) a short description and (d) date (of publication).

Rete di Economia Solidale
Un percorso da tracciare verso un'economia altra

Menu Principale
* Home
* Cosa' RES
* Distretti

Arece
* Documenti
* Gruppi tematici
* Rassegna stampa
* Recensione libri
* **Link**
* statistiche

Online
Abbiamo 11 ospiti e 0 iscritti in linea

Non siete registrati?
Potete farlo con un [click qui](#).

Login
Username
Password
 Log-in automatico [dalla prossima visita]

Registrazione
Recupero pswd smarrita.

Web Link

[Livello principale | Nuovo link | Novità | Popolari | Più richiesti | Random]

Categoria: [Inizio](#) / [Economia Solidale in Italia](#) / [Commercio Equo e Solidale](#)

Ordina per: Titolo (A/D) Data (A/D) Valutazione (A/D) Popolarità (A/D)
Ordinati per: Titolo (da A a Z)

AGICES - Assemblea Generale Commercio Equo #202
Descrizione: Associazione Assemblea Generale Italiana del Commercio Equo e Solidale
Pubblicato il: 17-Ott-2004 | Numero di richieste: 1022
[Segnala link interrotto](#)

Associazione Botteghe del Mondo #202
Descrizione: Associazione Italiana Botteghe del Mondo
Pubblicato il: 25-Dic-2003 | Numero di richieste: 1470
[Segnala link interrotto](#)

CensimEQUO #202
Descrizione: Censimento Botteghe del Mondo
Pubblicato il: 26-Apr-2007 | Numero di richieste: 747
[Segnala link interrotto](#)

Commercio Alternativo #202
Descrizione: Commercio Alternativo (importatore)
Pubblicato il: 26-Dic-2003 | Numero di richieste: 1092
[Segnala link interrotto](#)

CTM Altromercato #202
Descrizione: Consorzio CTM Altromercato (importatore)
Pubblicato il: 26-Dic-2003 | Numero di richieste: 1006
[Segnala link interrotto](#)

Equo Mercato #202
Descrizione: Equo Mercato (importatore)
Pubblicato il: 26-Dic-2003 | Numero di richieste: 1521
[Segnala link interrotto](#)

EquoLand #202

Figure 64. Snapshot from the Italian hub (<http://www.retecosol.org/>) with the information we extracted

Italian Hub 4 (<http://www.tempomat.it/>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any list of organizations. However, after clicking on the link reference with the title "Le Banche del Tempo in Italia", a new webpage with

several pages on organizations revealed. Each organization had a link to an internal webpage that contained more information about it (shown in Figure 65). We found 132 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, (d) e-mail address, (e) short description and (f) date (when the information for the organization have been updated).

Tempomat

Osservatorio Nazionale sulle Banche del Tempo

Dettagli Associazione

Associazione: **Associazione Culturale e Banca del Tempo** *Title*

Nata il: **18/11/1997** *Creation Date*

Indirizzo: **piazza Cereseto 7** *Contact Info*

Località: **15076 - Ovada (AL) - Piemonte** *Contact Info*

Telefono: **349 6130067** *Contact Info*

Fax: **+391782282878** *Contact Info*

Sito Web: **www.bancadeltampoidea.org** *Website URL*

E-Mail: **bdtidea2002@tiscali.it** *e-mail*

Numero Soci: Totali: **61** Uomini: 20 Donne: 40 Bambini fino a 12 anni: 1 Ragazzi fino a 20 anni: 0

Note: dati aggiornati al gennaio 2011
Scheda aggiornata al **09/02/2011**

[clicca qui](#) per tornare all'elenco

Figure 65. Snapshot from the Italian hub (<http://www.tempomat.it/>) with the information we extracted

Italian Hub 5 (<http://www.abitarenellacrisi.org/>)

The homepage of the hub did not contain any list of organizations. However, after clicking on “Chi e dove siamo / Sportelli” (found on the upper menu bar) a list of areas around Italy revealed; after clicking on each area the list of organizations that are located there are shown. Figure 66 shows the organizations that are located in Milan. The total number of organizations we found in the hub is 26 and they contain the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, and (d) e-mail address.

ABITARE NELLA CRISI Home Chi e dove siamo / Sportelli

Abitare nella Crisi Chi e dove siamo / Sportelli Milano

Milano

- Comitato Abitanti di San Siro**
 via Micene, 5 – San Siro, Milano
 sportello: martedì h.18-19
 assemblea: martedì h.19-20
 info: abitantisansiro@gmail.com – FB: Abitanti San Siro | Comitato Abitanti San Siro
 tel. emergenze: 327 2937274
- Comitato Lotta Casa Territorio Ticinese**
 via Torricelli – Ticinese, Milano
 martedì h.18-20
 FB: Comitato Lotta Casa Territorio
- As.I.A Milano**
 piazza Stuparich, 18 – Milano
 FB: ASIA Milano

Figure 66. Snapshot from the Italian hub (<http://www.abitarenellacrisi.org/>) with the information we extracted

Italian Hub 6 (<http://www.coworkingproject.com/>)

The list of organizations can be found after clicking on “TUTTI I COWO (MAPPA)”. This shows a map with references to all the corresponding organizations around Italy. We found 114 organizations containing information about (a) their title and (b) their website URL.

Visualizza [Coworking Cowo® in Italia e Svizzera](#) in una mappa di dimensioni maggiori

Piemonte

- [Coworking Cowo CUNEO/Login - Piazza Europa 22](#)
- [Coworking Cowo OMEGNA/Gravellona Toce – Piazzale Maulini 6](#)
- [Coworking Cowo TORINO/Bamboo - Corso Francia 224](#)
- [Coworking Cowo TORINO/Bliss – Strade Basse di Dora 42 \(Piazza Massaua\)](#)
- [Coworking Cowo TORINO/Caselle - via C.Craverio 69](#)
- [Coworking Cowo TORINO/Corso Regina Margherita - Corso Regina](#)

Figure 67. Snapshot from the Italian hub (<http://www.coworkingproject.com/>)

Italian Hub 7 (<http://www.coworkingfor.com/>)

The footer of the website of the hub contains a list areas around Italy. After clicking on any of them the organizations that are located in this area are shown; Figure 68 shows an indicative screenshot. We found 209 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information and (d) a short description.

Figure 68. Snapshot from the Italian hub (<http://www.coworkingfor.com/>) with the information we extracted

Italian Hub 8 (<http://www.assoziazionenazionalebdt.it/>)

The homepage of the website contained a reference with the title “Elenco delle Banche del Tempo in Italia” that revealed a list of time-banks in various areas around Italy organized according to their location. Figure 69 shows an indicative screenshot. We found 303 time-banks containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) e-mail address, (d) contact information and (e) the city/province they are located in.

Figure 69. Snapshot from the Italian hub (<http://www.associazionenazionalebdt.it>) with the information we extracted

Italian Hub 9 (<http://www.altromercato.it/it>)

The homepage of the website did not contain any list of organizations. However after clicking on the link with title “tutti i punti vendita” (found in the middle of the webpage) we found a map with a list of 7 organizations. Figure 70 shows an indicative screenshot. We found 7 time-banks containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) e-mail address, and (d) contact information.

Figure 70. Snapshot from the Italian hub (<http://www.altromercato.it/it>) with the information we extracted

Italian Hub 10 (<https://romattiva.wordpress.com/centrisocialiroma>)

The homepage of the website contained a list of social centers around Rome. Figure 71 shows an indicative screenshot. We found 61 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) e-mail address, and (d) contact information.

Figure 71. Snapshot from the Italian hub (<https://romattiva.wordpress.com/centrisocialiroma>) with the information we extracted

Italian Hub 11 (<http://www.bilancidigiustizia.it/>)

This website is actually a network of family groups practicing alternative economic choices. Although it seems to be an individual website describing their activities, it contains some links to other websites that can be found after clicking on SITI AMICI (found on the menu bar). In total we found 11 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) a short description, (d) contact information and (e) e-mail address.

Italian Hub 12 (<http://www.cooperazione.net/>)

This website is actually a center for cooperative activities. Although it seems to be an individual website describing their activities, it contains some links to other websites that can be found after clicking on LINK (found on the menu bar). In total we found 7 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) a short description, (d) contact information and (e) e-mail address.

Italian Hub 13 (<http://www.punk4free.org/concerti/elenco-locali-e-centri-sociali.html>)

This website contains a list of various social centers. Figure 72 shows an indicative screenshot. In total we found 849 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, and (c) contact information.

Figure 72. Snapshot from the Italian hub (<http://www.punk4free.org/concerti/elenco-locali-e-centri-sociali.html>) with the information we extracted

Italian Individual Websites

The list of individual websites has been analyzed manually. This means that we extracted manually information about the corresponding organizations after visiting them in a web browser. However we noticed that some of the individual websites were actually hub containing list of other organizations (i.e. http://www.altreconomia.it/site/fr_contenuto_detail.php?intId=2913, <http://www.associazionenazionalebdt.it/>, <http://www.altromercato.it/it>). The analysis of the individual websites revealed 864 organizations and we extracted the following information: (a) the title, (b) the website URL, (c) contact information, (d) e-mail address and (e) a short description.

The only problem we faced with the individual websites is that we could not analyze the following website because it no longer exists.

- <http://www.reteambientalesociale.org>

5.9 UK Networks

UK Hub 1 (<http://www.homelessuk.org/search/searchService.asp?ds=1>)

This hub provides a search service that assists users to find organizations according to several criteria. So we used this service without providing any keywords and this returned all the organizations. Each organization in the results space contains a reference link that opens a new webpage containing more information about the corresponding organization. Figure 73 shows an indicative screenshot of such a webpage. We found 7243 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, (d) e-mail address and (e) a short description.

The screenshot shows the Homeless UK website interface. The header includes the logo, navigation links like 'Log in | Register', and a search bar. A secondary navigation bar contains 'FIND A SERVICE', 'INFORMATION & RESEARCH', 'ABOUT THE SITE', and 'MY ACCOUNT'. Below this, there are more specific search options: 'WHO CAN HELP?', 'SEARCH ALL SERVICES', 'ACCOMMODATION SEARCH', 'EMERGENCY', and 'HELP'. The main content area displays search results for '2000 COMMUNITY ACTION CENTRE'. The results are organized into sections: 'LINKS', 'Address', 'Phone', 'Fax', 'Email', 'Website', 'Service offered', and 'Description'. Red boxes highlight the extracted information: the title '2000 COMMUNITY ACTION CENTRE', the address '199-201 Grove Street, Deptford, London SE8 3PG', the phone number '020 8692 2760', the fax number '020 8691 8611', the email address 'contact@2000cac.com', the website URL 'http://www.2000cac.com/', and the service description: 'Community centre for local residents. Information leaflets and signposting on a range of subjects, including social welfare, benefits, money and debt, housing, education, employment and health issues. Childcare services, after school clubs, health and fitness clubs. Meeting venue for older people's groups, residents' associations and youth forums. Internet access for older people.'

Figure 73. Snapshot from the English hub (<http://www.homelessuk.org/search/searchService.asp?ds=1>) with the information we extracted

UK Hub 2 (<http://www.self-help.org.uk/search/>)

This hub provides a search service that assists users to find organizations according to several criteria. So we used this service without providing any keywords and this returned all the organizations. Each organization in the results space contains a reference link that opens a new webpage containing more information about the corresponding organization. Figure 74 shows an indicative screenshot of such a webpage. We found 2227 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, (d) e-mail address and (e) a short description.

The screenshot shows the Self Help UK website interface. The header includes the logo and tagline 'The guide to patient support and self help'. A navigation menu at the top lists: HOME, SEARCH, DIRECTORY, ADD YOUR ORGANISATION, SELF HELP BOOKS, USEFUL RESOURCES, HEALTH JOBS, ABOUT US. The main content area displays search results for 'Action for Blind People'. A sidebar on the left contains a search box and a menu with options like 'Welcome', 'Directory', 'Add your organisation', etc. The search results table lists various details for the organization, with red boxes highlighting specific information and red text labels indicating the type of data extracted.

Field	Value	Label
Organisation name	Action for Blind People	Title
Description	Action for Blind People is a national charity providing free and confidential support for blind and partially sighted people in all aspects of their lives. One call to Action means help with anything from finding a job, applying for benefits, housing issues to information on local services.	Description
Street address	14-16 Verney Rd	Contact Info
City/Town	London	
Postcode	SE16 3DZ	
Web Address	www.actionforblindpeople.org.uk	Website URL
Email	info@actionforblindpeople.org.uk	e-mail
Main Phone No	020 7635 4800	Contact Info
Helpline Number	0800 915 4666	

Figure 74. Snapshot from the English hub (<http://www.self-help.org.uk/search/>) with the information we extracted

UK Hub 3 (<http://locality.org.uk/members/>)

The hub contains a map with all the available resources. Each pin on the map represents a single organization. Each pin is clickable and once clicked a new pop-up window will show up containing a description of the organization and a link to an internal webpage containing more information about the corresponding organization. This is the information we extracted and is shown in Figure 75 (in red rectangles the particular information we extracted). We found 700 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, (d) e-mail address and (e) a short description.

Figure 75. Snapshot from the English hub (<http://locality.org.uk/members/>) with the information we extracted

UK Hub 4 (<http://www.dtascot.org.uk/content/directory-of-members/directory>)

The hub contains a list of organizations, sorted in alphabetical order. Each organization in the list contains a link (with the name “Read more”) that points to a new internal webpage that contains more information about the organization. Figure 76 shows an indicative screenshot of such an internal webpage with the information we extracted (shown in red rectangles). We found 230 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, (d) e-mail address, (e) short description and (f) the date that the organization has been established.

Figure 76. Snapshot from the English hub (<http://www.dtascot.org.uk/content/directory-of-members/directory>) with the information we extracted

UK Hub 5 (<http://www.dtawales.org.uk/by-name/>)

The hub contains a list of organizations, sorted in alphabetical order. Each organization in the list is actually a reference that points to a new internal webpage that contains more information about the organization. Figure 77 shows an indicative screenshot of such an internal webpage with the information we extracted (shown in red rectangles). We found 40 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, (d) e-mail address, and (e) short description.

The screenshot shows the webpage for ACE: Action in Caerau & Ely. The page is titled "ACE: Action in Caerau & Ely" and includes a navigation menu with options like "Truists", "ch", "ging Members", "Location Map", "Authority", "Enterprise", "ibers", and "nd by members". The main content area displays the following information:

- Title:** ACE: Action in Caerau & Ely
- Address:** 4 Grand Avenue, Ely, Cardiff, CF5 4BL
- Contact Info:** Tel: 02920 873 664
- Email:** info@elycaerau.com
- Website URL:** www.alycaerau.com
- Description:** Managing local services and generating income...

The description also includes a brief overview of the organization's mission and aims:

ace (Action in Caerau & Ely) is a new organisation created through the Ely and Caerau Communities First programme. ace is looking at a range of different projects and activities to regenerate and improve our community.

It aims to:

- Bring the community together
- Support community groups
- Manage and develop local projects
- Employ staff and create local employment opportunities
- Manage community buildings
- Promote the needs of Ely and Caerau with the Council and other service providers

Figure 77. Snapshot from the English hub (<http://www.dtawales.org.uk/by-name/>) with the information we extracted

UK Hub 6 (<http://www.uk.coop/directory>)

This hub provides a search service that assists users in finding organizations according to several criteria. So we used this service without providing any keywords and this returned all the organizations. Each organization in the results space contains a reference link that opens a new webpage containing more information about the corresponding organization. Figure 78 shows an indicative screenshot of such a webpage. We found 12717 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information and (e) a short description.

ABCUL *Title*

Oth

- ABCU Holyoa
- Co-op Holyoa
- Loop : Holyoa
- The G 2nd Flc Manch
- The G Corpori

Description

ABCUL is the principal association representing the interests of Credit Unions in the United Kingdom. Credit Unions are financial co-operatives owned and controlled by their members. They offer savings and great value loans plus they are local, ethical and know what their members want. Each Credit Union has a common bond which determines who can join it. The common bond may be for people living or working in the same area, people working for the same employer or people who belong to the same association, such as a church or trade union. As financial co-operatives, credit unions are part of the long established and fast growing co-operative movement in Britain.

Registered Address

Holyoake House Hanover Street
Manchester
Manchester
M60 0AS
United Kingdom

Contact Info

Directory Category Business, Money

Organisation ID R000041

Website www.abcuk.coop *Website URL*

Updated: 29/06/2015

Share this

- Share
- Tweet
- Recommend

Figure 78. Snapshot from the English hub (<http://www.uk.coop/directory>) with the information we extracted

UK Hub 7 (<http://buysocialdirectory.org.uk/directory>)

The hub contains a list of organizations, sorted in alphabetical order. Each organization in the list is actually a reference that points to a new internal webpage that contains more information about the organization. Figure 79 shows an indicative screenshot of such an internal webpage with the information we extracted (shown in red rectangles). We found 8556 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, and (c) contact information.

Figure 79. Snapshot from the English hub (<http://buysocialdirectory.org.uk/directory>) with the information we extracted

UK Hub 8 (<http://www.mygreendirectory.info/listing/location/united-kingdom>)

The hub contains a list of organizations, splitted in several pages. Figure 80 shows an indicative screenshot of one organization with the information we extracted (shown in red rectangles). Of course we extracted the information for all the organizations by visiting all the available pages of results. We found 1858 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information and (d) a short description.

Figure 80. Snapshot from the English hub (<http://www.mygreendirectory.info/listing/location/united-kingdom>) with the information we extracted

UK Hub 9 (<http://www.letslinkuk.net/regions/uk-map.htm>)

The hub contains an interactive map (shown in Figure 81) that allows the user to first restrict his choices to a specific area of interest (i.e. a city in UK) and then inspect the organizations that are located in this area. This requires several clicks from the user and furthermore the list of organizations is not always given homogeneously. For these reasons we could not extract the organizations in an automatic way from this hub.

Figure 81. Snapshot from the English hub (<http://www.letslinkuk.net/regions/uk-map.htm>)

UK Hub 10 (<http://www.communityshops.coop/shops>)

The hub contains an interactive map that shows the locations of the various organizations. The organizations can also be viewed as a list after clicking on the tab with the name "Shops List". Each organization refers to an internal webpage that contains more information about it. Figure 82 shows an indicative screenshot of the webpage of an organization. We found 336 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, and (d) the date that each organization opened.

Figure 82. Snapshot from the English hub (<http://www.communityshops.coop/shops>) with the information we extracted

UK Hub 11 (<http://animalrightasuk.org/localanimalrightsgroups.html>)

The hub contains a list of organizations categorized according to their location. Each organization is a link that opens a new pop-up window containing information about the corresponding organization (shown in Figure 83). We found 101 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, and (d) e-mail address.

Figure 83. Snapshot from the English hub (<http://animalrightasuk.org/localanimalrightsgroups.html>) with the information we extracted

UK Hub 12 (<http://www.transitionnetwork.org/initiatives/by-number>)

The hub contains a list of organizations. Each organization contains a link that points to an internal webpage that contains more information about it. Figure 84 shows an indicative screenshot of such a webpage. We found 460 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, and (d) a short description.

The screenshot shows the website for Totnes Transition Town. Red boxes highlight the following information:

- Title:** Totnes
- Contact Info:** 43 Fore Street, Totnes TQ9 5HN, United Kingdom
- Description:** Transition Town Totnes (TTT) is the world's first Transition Town. We started work in 2006, since when 39 projects have emerged, engaging an estimated 3270 residents and generating a conservatively estimated £861,000 income to the town and district. We have recently launched *Transition in Action*, the print and online publication of our Energy Descent Action Plan which is available to view and purchase at www.totnesedap.org. This is not a document designed to gather dust and we are quickly taking the project into implementation phase. We are currently recruiting for a Transition in Action Project Manager, thanks to renewed funding by the Esmee Fairbairn Foundation, but there are still holes in our fundraising needs and, whilst historic, this is a financially critical time for TTT and we are now fundraising for some essential components of this project. Transition in Action offers a number of opportunities for funders and investors to engage in this process and these are outlined in the attached PDF document.
- Website URL:** <http://www.transitiontowntotnes.org>

Figure 84. Snapshot from the English hub (<http://www.transitionnetwork.org/initiatives/by-number>) with the information we extracted

UK Hub 13 (<http://www.globaljustice.org.uk/contact-local-group>)

The hub contains a list of organizations categorized according to their location. The only information we could extract from the hub is (a) the title of the organization, (b) the website URL of the organization and (c) the area. In total we found 49 organizations.

Figure 85. Snapshot from the English hub (<http://www.transitionnetwork.org/initiatives/by-number>)

UK Hub 14 (<http://www.ethicalconsumer.org/boycotts/boycottlist.aspx>)

The hub contains a list of organizations, sorted in alphabetical order. Figure 86 shows an indicative screenshot of the list. We found 65 organizations with the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, and (e) short description.

Ethical Consumer list of consumer boycotts
 The most comprehensive English language list of progressive boycotts, with links to campaigns, alternative products and more information about companies and brands. Boycotts are one of the **four types of ethical buying**.
 If your boycott isn't listed please **email the news editor** with any relevant information (inclusion does not constitute an endorsement by Ethical Consumer).

Boycotts A-Z Jump Menu
 A/B/C/D/E/F/G/H/I/J/K/L/M/N/O/P/Q/R/S/T/U/V/W/X/Y/Z

Adidas	Title
Category: Animal Rights	Description
Called by: Viva	Boycott call from Viva for using kangaroo skin to make some types of football boots. Adidas are phasing out the use of kangaroo leather by 98 per cent over 12 months but will still use small amounts of it so the boycott continues.
Detailed Company Profile (subscribers only): Adidas AG	Website URL
Company Profile (free to view): Adidas AG	
Related Product Guides: sportswear and sportswear trainers.	

Figure 86. Snapshot from the English hub (<http://www.ethicalconsumer.org/boycotts/boycottlist.aspx>) with the information we extracted

UK Hub 15

http://www.stonewall.org.uk/at_home/whats_in_my_area/default.asp

This hub provides a search service that assists users in finding organizations. So we used this service without providing any keywords and this returned all the organizations. Figure 87 shows the list of organizations. We found 709 organizations containing the following information: (a) title, (b) website URL, (c) contact information, (d) e-mail address and (e) a short description.

What's in my area?
 Resources for community groups
 Add your community group to What's in my area
 Accessing legal advice
 Prides and Mardi gras
 Add your law firm's details to Stonewall's what's in my area database

What's it got to do with you?
 What's it got to do with me?
 Get Involved
 Engaging Gay People in Your Work
 Charity Funding
 Guide for Gay Visitors
 Civil Partnerships-overview

Region: [dropdown] Category: [dropdown] SEARCH

Search results
 Region: All Category: All

<p>4 Playsquash 4 Play Squash is a London based squash group for gay and lesbian squash players and their friends. The group welcomes players of all ability levels. Postal address: None given. Email: info@4playsquash.org Web: http://www.4playsquash.org/index.php Region: London Category: Arts and leisure</p>	<p>Phoenix - A Trans Support Group for Kent PHOENIX - A Trans Support Group For Kent A friendly place to meet for chat / coffee in a secure venue on the first Sunday of each month from 1600 - 1900. Free parking and changing facilities available. Cost £5 per person. Tea/ Coffee 50p per cup. Venue address Lower Rd, Northfleet, Kent DA11 9BL . Contact Becky Essex 07595 159108. beckytvessex@yahoo.co.uk A Beaumont Society Supported Group. Postal address: Walk Tall Lower Road, Northfleet, Kent DA11 9B Telephone: 07595 159108 Opening hours: PHOENIX-A monthly support group held in Kent UK on the first Sunday of each month between 1600 - 1900. Email: beckytvessex@yahoo.co.uk Web: www.facebook.com/phoenixtranskent Region: South East England</p>
--	---

Related topics
 → Resources for community groups
 → Prides and Mardi Gras
 → Add your community group

If you cannot find the information you need on this website, you can call our info line on 08000 50 20 20 (Mon-Fri 9:30am - 5:30pm) and we will try to point you in the right direction.

Figure 87. Snapshot from the English hub (http://www.stonewall.org.uk/at_home/whats_in_my_area/default.asp) with the information we extracted

UK Individual Websites

The list of individual websites has been analyzed manually. This means that we extracted manually information about the corresponding organizations after visiting them in a web browser. The analysis of the individual websites revealed 5 organizations and we extracted the following information: (a) the title, (b) the website URL, (c) contact information including address, postal code and telephone numbers, (d) e-mail address and (e) the dates that the organization has been active.

6 Merging the list of organizations

After extracting the information about the organizations from one hub, we stored them as CSV values in an XLS file. This means that for each country we encountered several files. The next obvious step was to merge these lists into a single one. Apart from merging them we also had to remove the duplicate occurrences of the organizations. For this reason we exploited the OpenRefine tool. We used the title of the organizations and the website URLs to determine if there are duplicates.

After merging the lists for each country we stored them in a single Excel file. Each file contained the following sheets:

- Sheet with name **“with URLs”**: It consists of all the organizations that contain a website URL
- Sheet with name **“without URLs”**: It consists of all the organizations that do not contain a website URL
- Sheet with name **“All”**: It consists of all the organizations. Practically it is a merged list containing the organizations of the two previous sheets.

7 Downloading the websites of organizations

Apart from extracting information for the lists of organizations from the hubs, it was required to download the contents of the website of the identified organizations. This would allow: (a) the offline accessibility and processing the organizations and (b) the scientific verification of the analysis process. As regards the latter, it was important to download the contents of the website, since the internet is a rather unstable environment where websites that are available today, might not be there in future (even after a few days). Furthermore in order to control the size of the downloaded websites, since they could contain a lot of information (in terms of hyperlinks that refer to other content), we decided to download only the homepage of the website; this is the content that a user can see after visiting a website using his web browser.

We had two different alternatives for downloading the websites. More specifically we could download:

- a. the original files of the websites (i.e. HTML files, CSS files, images, etc.). This option would result in the creation of a folder containing the corresponding files for each website.

- b. the homepage of the website and transform it into a PDF document. This option would result in the construction of a single PDF file for each organization.

For option (a) we could use the tool GNU Wget (see Section 3.5) while for option (b) we could use the tool WKhtmlTOPdf (see section 3.6). Each option has pros and cons; option (a) offers more flexibility since we can specify how many contents of a website will be downloaded (i.e. download the contents after following the links recursively) however it will end up downloading a lot of files for a given website. On the other hand option (b) downloads only a specific part of a website however it is more convenient for offline reading since it produces a single PDF file that can be easily be reviewed and printed in paper. Considering that our purpose was to download only the homepage of each website, we decided to follow option (b).

We used the tool WKhtmlTOPdf for downloading the contents of the websites of the organizations for all the countries. Some of the websites have not been downloaded. This happens because: (a) their access was forbidden during the downloading process (June-July 2015) or (b) the websites were not active any more or (c) the websites contain dynamic contents that cannot be stored or printed for offline reading (i.e. content that requires flash player). The filename of the downloaded websites has the following format: **ID-websiteURL.pdf**, where ID is the value of the organization as it can be found in the produced Excel file (in the sheet “with URLs”) and websiteURL is the value of the URL as it can be found in the same sheet of the Excel file, after removing some of its characters, so that it can be used as a filename. An example (taken from the Greek network) is 10-http__symplefsi_org.pdf.

Upon the completion of the above process we inspected the lists of websites that were not downloaded and executed the above process again using them as input. The second run was necessary for ensuring that we downloaded all the websites we could; therefore we would like to eliminate the issue that certain sites were not available for a short period during the downloading process, but were active after a while.

8 Conclusions

The main purpose of this deliverable was to describe the process for the analysis of the wide range of networks, organizations and groups engaged in “alternative forms of resilience” as seen in recent solidarity and other social innovation practices across the nine countries which are involved in the project (e.g. barter networks, food banks, time banks, alternative coins, free medical services, soup kitchens, etc.)

The process included 3 main activities: (a) extracting particular information about such organizations and groups as they can be found from a set of representative hubs, and storing them in a form suitable for further analysis (in an Excel File) (b) merging the produced lists into a single one, and omitting any duplicate occurrences of an organization, and (c) downloading the contents of the organizations that can be found online (through their website).

The outcome that will be distributed to the LiveWHAT consortium is: (a) one Excel file for each country, containing the (merged) list of organizations that were found for each country, (b) one Excel file for each country, containing the organizations that were found for each hub; the results of each hub will be stored as a separate sheet in the file, (c) the pdf documents that contain the contents of the downloaded websites, and (d) the present deliverable that describes the entire process.